

Dissertation submitted to the department of Architecture

***‘Gap analyses of work in progress BIM deliverables on
the NMIS project at RIBA Stage 5’***

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**Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
MSC ADVANCED CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGIES & BIM**

Title:

‘Gap analyses of work in progress BIM deliverables on the NMIS project at RIBA Stage 5’

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Declaration of Authorship

MSC ADVANCED CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGIES & BIM

Declaration

"I hereby declare that this submission is my own work and has been composed by myself. It contains no unacknowledged text and has not been submitted in any previous context. All quotations have been distinguished by quotation marks and all sources of information, text, illustration, tables, images etc. have been specifically acknowledged.

I accept that if having signed this Declaration my work should be found at Examination to show evidence of academic dishonesty the work will fail, and I will be liable to face the University Senate Discipline Committee."

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Abstract

Began in 2011, when the UK Government decided to take a programme of measures to reduce costs and make the construction sector more efficient. Collaborative 3D BIM implementation got mandated on Publically procured construction projects, with BIM Level 2 being developed to meet this mandate. Nevertheless, this research evaluates current literature review connecting BIM, FM & IRs to compare Pre-appointment BEP vs Post-appointment BEP and carries out gap analyses of BIM Deliverables against those BEPs on the NMIS project, which enabled to produce a guide to initiating BIM activities by the responsible parties at the right phases.

Moreover, to answer research questions mixed methods are adapted. First method of quantitative methodology is executed through Literature review referring to connection between BIM, FM & AM, including the importance of early engagement of Facilities Managers, as well as challenges & benefits of BIM in FM. In addition to the IR documents being explained, typical BIM deliverables are defined, including content of the BEP and types of BIM audits being typically carried out on projects. The literature review established a high-reliability resource to support gap analyses on a live NMIS project at RIBA Stage 5. The second pragmatic qualitative methodology enables to collect necessary information either from the Contractor and Client's teams via e-mails and meetings to examine IRs, BIM Execution Plans and selected BIM deliverables.

Considerately, the research raises serious of questions, whether the information produced by all project stakeholders on the NMIS project is sufficient. Therefore, the paper demonstrates via Case Study how gaps within BIM deliverables could be audited for, to gain understanding what the Clients would be missing out on, assuming that the audits/checks are not carried out on BIM-enabled projects. Consequently, from clients' perspective, this research paper highlights the need of utilising the proposed guidance to aid projects from the outset continuously to O&M of a facility/infrastructure. The results showed that the current state of the collected post-appointment BEP from the NMIS project is found to contain limited details to support the delivery of BIM deliverables. Results also revealed that the Building Services 3D BIM Model as well as COBie Data sheet have been delivered in partial alignment with that post-appointment BEP as well as when comparing the model against the COBie data sheet and MAL.

Thanks to huge availability to implement BIM across the whole life cycle of a facility/infrastructure to meet Client's expectation at every information exchange, which ultimately leads to better operation & maintenance of a facility/infrastructure. Therefore, the study concludes that the most important action for Clients, Contractor & Design Teams is to follow the proposed 'Future projects guidance' through a consistent and planned approach to implement BIM from the outset of a project, continuously through Design, Construction and Operation & Maintenance of the facility/infrastructure, rather than focusing entirely on Design and Construction phases.

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List of Contents

Declaration of Authorship.....	2
Abstract	3
Acknowledgments.....	4
List of Contents.....	5
List of Tables/Figures	7
List of Abbreviations	8
Terminology – guidance.....	9
1.0 INTRODUCTION	10
1.0.1 Why is BIM significant for Facilities Management (FM).....	11
1.0.2 What is to be achieved by the end of the research?.....	12
1.1 Background to the Study.....	13
1.1.1 National Manufacturing Institute Scotland (NMIS) – Live Project	14
1.1.2 Information Requirements (IR).....	17
1.1.3 Facilities Management (FM)	18
1.1.4 Building Information Modelling (BIM)	19
1.1.5 UK GOV BIM Mandate.....	20
1.2 Research Methodology	22
1.2.1 What did these methods allow to achieve?.....	22
1.2.2 Benefits of using this methodology	22
1.2.3 Considerations and measures for Data protection	22
1.3 Research Limitations	23
1.4 Motivation to this Research.....	23
1.5 The aim of this Research	23
1.6 Objectives of the Research	23
1.7 Research Questions.....	23
1.8 Research Structure	24
2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW	25
2.1 Relationship between BIM, FM & AM.....	26
2.2 Facility Managers’ engagement in the early phases of a project	27
2.3 Challenges & Benefits of BIM in FM	28
2.4 IR documents to be included at the outset of a project	31
2.5 Typical Lead Appointed Party’s BIM Deliverables at ie	33
2.6 BIM Execution Plan (BEP) content	37
2.7 Types of BIM Reviews	39
2.8 Synthesis of the Literature Review	41

2.9	Summary	42
3.0	GAP ANALYSES – NMIS PROJECT (Case Study)	43
3.1	Level 1 Analysis – Appointing Party’s IRs	43
3.1.1	IRs included at the outset of a project	44
3.2	Level 1 Analysis – Appointed Party’s BIM Execution Plan (BEP)	45
3.2.1	Pre-appointment BEP	46
3.2.2	Post-appointment BEP	48
3.2.3	Pre-appointment BEP vs Post-appointment BEP	50
3.3	Level 2 Analysis – Lead Appointed Party’s BIM Deliverables	51
3.3.1	Information Model – audit.....	54
3.3.2	COBie Data Sheet – asset data validation	58
3.3.3	Information Model vs COBie Data Sheet vs MAL.....	63
3.4	Future projects Guidance.....	65
4.0	DISCUSSING ANALYSES	67
5.0	CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS	69
	REFERENCES.....	70

List of Tables/Figures

Table 1	– Table displays difference between previous BS/PAS and latest BS EN ISO standards.....	9
Table 2	– List of Appointed Parties awarded by UoS on the NMIS project.....	16
Table 3	– List of current & superseded BIM Standards.....	20
Table 4	– Maturity stages.....	21
Table 5	– List of BIM implementation challenges.....	28
Table 6	– List of BIM implementation benefits.....	29
Table 7	– List of required IR documents to be established.....	31
Table 8	– Protocol to be included as part of Suite of IRs at Tender.....	31
Table 9	– other documents to be included as part of Suite of IRs.....	31
Table 10	– List of typical BIM Deliverables + when & why they are required.....	33
Table 11	– BEP’s list of content.....	37
Table 12	– Types of BIM Reviews.....	40
Table 13	– Types of IRs included at the outset of a project.....	44
Table 14	– Pre-appointment BEP Audit.....	46
Table 15	– Post-appointment BEP Audit.....	48
Table 16	– Alignment check of Post-appointment BEP against Pre-appointment BEP.....	50
Table 17	– MEP Information Model Audit against BEPs.....	54
Table 18	– COBie Data Sheet validation against BEPs & MAL.....	58
Table 19	– Asset Validation between Information Model, COBie Data Sheet and MAL.....	63
Table 20	– Guidance to implementing BIM for accurate deployment of FM from the outset of a project.....	65
Figure 1	– External image of the NMIS – front.....	14
Figure 2	– External image of the NMIS - back.....	14
Figure 3	– External image of the NMIS – side.....	14
Figure 4	– Internal image within the NMIS – manufacturing hall.....	14
Figure 5	– Internal image within the NMIS – public entrance.....	15
Figure 6	– Information Requirements skeleton, Guidance Part D.....	17
Figure 7	– 3D image from the MEP Information Model of the NMIS project at RIBA Stage 5.....	51
Figure 8	– Interior of the NMIS project + Information Model of the exact space within Dalux.....	52
Figure 9	– Interior of the NMIS project + Information Model of the exact space within Dalux.....	53

List of Abbreviations

AEC - Architecture, Engineering and Construction
AIM - Asset Information Model
AIR - Asset Information Requirement
AM - Asset Management
BEP - BIM Execution Plan
BIM - Building Information Model / Modelling /Management
BS - British Standard
CAD - Computer Aided Design
CAFM - Computer Aided Facilities Management System
CDE - Common Data Environment
CIC - Construction Industry Council
COBie - Construction Operations Building Information Exchange
DfMA - Design for Manufacture and Assembly
EIM - Employer’s Information Manager
EIR - Exchange Information Requirements (formerly Employer’s Information Requirements)
FM - Facilities Management
HLM – HLM Architects (Designers/Appointed Party)
IAM - The Institute of Asset Management
ie - information exchange
IFC - Industry Foundation Classes
IM - Information Management / Project Information Manager
IMP - Information Management Process
IP - Information Protocol
IR - Information Requirements
ITM - Task Team Interface Manager
ISO - International Standards
LOD - Level of Detail /Development
LOI - Level of Information
MAL - Maintainable Asset List
MCL - Morrison Construction (Contractor/Lead Appointed Party)
MEP - Mechanical, Electrical and Plumbing
MIDP - Master Information Delivery Plan
NBS - National Building Specification
NMIS - National Manufacturing Institute Scotland (Live Project)
OIR - Organisational Information Requirements
PAS - Publically available Specification
PIM - Project Information Model
PIP - Project Implementation Plan
PIR - Project Information Requirements
RIBA - Royal Institute of British Architects
RIBA PoW - RIBA Plan of Work
Rvt - Revit software format
SIR - Security Information Requirements
SMP - Standards, Methods and Procedures
TIDP - Task Information Delivery Plan
TIM - Task Team Information Manager
Uniclass - Unified Classification System
UoS – University of Strathclyde (Client/Appointing Party)
WIP - Work in Progress

Terminology – guidance

The below table 1 displays the difference in terminology between BS/PAS 1192 and BS EN ISO 19650 suite of Standards as per ‘Transition guidance to BS EN ISO 19650’ document (BSI, PD 19650-0:2019):

<i>BS/PAS 1192 (previous term)</i>	<i>BS EN ISO 19650 (new term)</i>
Employer, Client, Asset Owner	APPOINTING PARTY
Contract	APPOINTMENT
BIM Level 1, 2, 3 etc.	BIM STAGE 1, 2, 3 etc.
Project Team	DELIVERY TEAM
Employer’s Information Requirements (EIR)	EXCHANGE INFORMATION REQUIREMENTS (EIR)
Volume strategy	FEDERATION STRATEGY
Role	FUNCTION
Graphical / non-graphical	GEOMETRICAL / NON-GEOMETRICAL
Standard method and procedure (SMP)	INFORMATION STANDARD & INFORMATION PRODUCTION METHOD AND PROCEDURE
Supplier	LEAD APPOINTED PARTY (TIER 1) / APPOINTED PARTY (TIER 2)
Level of Definition (LOD/LOI)	LEVEL OF INFORMATION NEED
Post-contract BIM Execution Plan (BEP)	POST-APPOINTMENT BIM EXECUTION PLAN (BEP)
Pre-contract BIM Execution Plan (BEP)	PRE-APPOINTMENT BIM EXECUTION PLAN (BEP)
Plain Language Questions (PLQ)	PROJECT INFORMATION REQUIREMENTS (PIR)
Information Requirements (IR)	SUITE OF OIR, AIR, PIR & EIR DOCUMENTS
Suitability	STATUS

Table 1 – Table displays difference between previous BS/PAS and latest BS EN ISO standards (BSI, PD 19650-0:2019)

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This research focuses on finding out what Building Information Modelling (BIM) is in relation to Facilities Management (FM), which also communicates the challenges and benefits in implementing BIM for FM, as well as identifying gaps of handover deliverables relating to BIM, FM & IRs on the National Manufacturing Institute for Scotland (NMIS) project. Intriguingly, this research is vital for the Case Study of the NMIS project, which is currently halfway through construction works at RIBA Stage 5.

The research mainly comprises of qualitative data collection directly from the Morrison Construction's (MCL) BIM Team who has been the appointed Contractor aka Lead Appointed Party on the NMIS project. MCL offered to supply the researcher with all the data necessary such as information models in requested formats, COBie data and any relevant BIM documents. MCL also allowed for observations as part of a site visit of the NMIS facility to take pictures and find out more about the construction progress. MCL's project members also answered any real time queries relating to BIM deliverables. In addition, to evaluate the state of current knowledge on BIM, FM and IRs this research also consists of quantitative findings to support Literature review.

Moreover, case study focuses on gap analyses, where Pre-appointment BIM Execution Plan (BEP) and Post-appointment BIM Execution Plan BEP are reviewed separately against ISO 19650 as well as against each other to identify if all documents are in alignment in absence of the University of Strathclyde's (UoS) Information Requirements (IR). Then again, these BEPs are inspected in contrast to some BIM deliverables such as: an individual Information Model and COBie Data to determine whether the BIM deliverables are following IRs aka pre-appointment BEP agreed.

Nevertheless, this research attempts to fill the gap in the Literature review relating to how, by whom and when specific BIM activities are required to be performed for better FM deployment. For that reason, research analyses are being completed with the 'Future Projects guidance', recommending what steps are endorsed on a BIM-enabled project for successful completion of each RIBA stage.

Finally, this research will not cover any Quality Assurance (QA) Information Container Check, Availability of Reference Information & Shared Resources Check and Information Review as part of typical Task Team responsibilities; nor Information Model Review, Information handling - Audit trail and Design Coordination Review as part of Lead Appointed Party responsibilities; nor Capability & Capacity Review as well as Project Information Model (PIM) Audit as part of Appointing Parties responsibilities and will focus on auditing BIM Execution Plan (BEP), Information Model Audit as well as Asset Data.

1.0.1 Why is BIM significant for Facilities Management (FM)

According to Bloodworth Rivers (2020) there are many professions where the basic responsibilities of the function throughout someone's career essentially remain the same, however with the rapid pace of new technologies, FM is not one of those professions and it no longer involves elementary activities. According to Neenu (2020) BIM requires input from Facilities Managers, so that the information generated during the process of design and construction is appropriate for the O&M needs. Therefore, the most significant aspect of BIM for FM is that Facility Managers get to be involved from the design stage, which in essence would improve the building outcome, whilst raising the profile of the FM function for the purpose of the Government Soft Landings (SWG, 2016).

Prior to BIM being introduced, FM has not been a very well-considered function during the lifecycle of a Construction project as Facilities Manager were rarely required to be involved during the Design or Construction. Nowadays, FM with the aid of BIM may turn into a very pleasant working environment as BIM processes and technologies allow for very accurate and necessary information to be delivered in a digital format, for that reason, training every Facilities Manager by taking them out of their comfort zone and becoming BIM active may seem like an essential move in 2022 within large organisations.

1.0.2 What is to be achieved by the end of the research?

According to Reche (2020) when BIM is precisely adopted it brings multiple benefits, exclusively around productivity even though implementing BIM in construction projects is still found to be very challenging due to knowledge gap. However, BIM promotes the creation of visualisations, sections, and elevations to incorporate this information later in the process of Construction and Operation & Maintenance (O&M) of facilities/assets/infrastructure (Reche, 2020).

Consequently, this dissertation brings about why defining IRs is so crucial on any project as setting the IRs seems to be a cumulative effect produced, when IRs initiate a succession of BIM deliverables. For that reason, the new knowledge from the Literature review and NMIS Case Study is brought to the attention of any Appointing Parties, Lead Appointed Parties and Delivery Teams to promote accurate BIM implementation approaches that follow standardised steps from the outset of a project to fully benefit the Planning, Design, Construction & O&M stages of any project, since the success of a project is highly dependent on how it was kicked-off. For that reason, filling this gap in the Literature review relating to how, by whom and when specific BIM activities is to be performed by producing a 'Future Projects guidance'.

1.1 Background to the Study

Chapter 1.1 introduces the NMIS project on which the case study is based on and further explains what different terminologies within AEC industry are, such as: Information Requirements (IR), Facilities Management (FM) as well as Building Information Modelling (BIM). It then moves on to clarifying what BIM Mandate comprises of and who is affected by this mandate, whilst finishing the chapter on BIM Standards that are required to be followed from the outset of any BIM-enabled project.

1.1.1 National Manufacturing Institute Scotland (NMIS) – Live Project

National Manufacturing Institute for Scotland (NMIS) is a Publically procured project with the completion value of £65m, hosted by the University of Strathclyde (UoS), and Strathclyde Business School (UoS, 2022). The below images present a current construction phase:

Figure 1 – External image of the NMIS - front (Juste, 2022)

Figure 2 – External image of the NMIS - back (Juste, 2022)

Figure 3 – External image of the NMIS - side (Juste, 2022)

Figure 4 – Interior image of the NMIS – manufacturing hall (Juste, 2022)

Figure 5 – Interior image of the NMIS – public entrance (Juste, 2022)

Moreover, the NMIS project is a Design & Build contract with novated Design Team during Construction Work, and the Morrison Construction (MCL) being responsible for the Design Team.

The NMIS has been awarded by the University of Strathclyde (UoS) as an Appointing Party to the following Organisations as shown in table 2 below (BSL, 2021):

ORGANISATION	FUNCTION	BS EN ISO 19650-2 - CODE	ORIGINATOR
Morrison Construction	Contractor Construction Lead Lead Appointed Party	W (Contractor)	MCL
HLM Architects	Design Lead Architect Appointed Party	DL (Design Lead) A (Architect)	HLM
Davie + McCulloch Ltd.	Electrical Services Engineer Mechanical Services Engineer Appointed Party	E (Electrical Engineer) M (Mechanical Engineer)	DML
Waterman Group	Civil Engineer Structural Engineer Appointed Party	C (Civil Engineer) S (Structural Engineer)	WSL
Bimsense Ltd.	Information manager Appointed Party	N (Information Manager)	BSL

Table 2 – List of Appointed Parties awarded by UoS on the NMIS project (BSL, 2021):

According to NMIS (2022) this facility is the future of manufacturing that will improve skills of current & future workforce, as the industry, academia, and the public sector work collaboratively on innovative research to revolutionise productivity levels and to attract investment and make Scotland a global leader in advanced manufacturing (UoS, 2019). The NMIS project is deemed to be the state-of-the-art facility comprised of the following (UoS, 2019):

- **The Digital Factory 2050** - industry led centre for collaborative manufacturing research, technology, and solution development
- **The Innovation Collaboratory** (incorporating the ‘Forum’) - Industry led centre for manufacturing technology application and process development
- **The Manufacturing Skills Academy** - Scotland’s hub for manufacturing skills and education
- **The “Forum”**- providing links to business support, to the One Scotland Partners and external organisations.

According to HLM (2019) the NMIS is an ambitious proposal aimed at shaping the future of manufacturing and innovation in Scotland. The proposal builds on the Scottish Government Strategy ‘A Manufacturing Future for Scotland’, as well as the UK Industrial Strategy and has been emerging through the NMIS Steering Committee. The new NMIS facilities will add to the existing AFRC facilities to provide a wider range of support for industrial partners (HLM, 2019).

The NMIS project commenced with Planning application in September 2019 (HLM, 2019), and the Construction began in November 2020 (BSL, 2021), whereas the Construction works were expected to be completed in June 2022, however, there has been a slight delay with handing it over to the UoS. The facility is expected to be approx. 11,500m² GIFA, which sits on an 11-acre site. (UoS, 2019), built on AMIDS Netherton Farm, Abbotsinch Road, Renfrew, PA4 9PA. This digital facility is adjacent to Glasgow International Airport and will have good access to road rail and air connections.

1.1.2 Information Requirements (IR)

According to Leygonie, et al. (2021) Information Requirements (IR) are the foundation from which the Appointing Party's expectation would be defined in relation to Information models delivered, whereas ISO 19650-1 (2018) defines IRs as the specification for what, when, how and for whom the information is to be formed in relation to organizational objectives, operation of an asset, delivery of an asset and appointment of the Lead Appointed Party and its Delivery Team. According to the UK BIM Framework (2021) within Guidance Part D, IRs are like a frame containing many openings of different shapes and sizes. These 'openings' specify the requirements of the information needed to fill them accordingly so that Delivery Teams comply with the Appointing Parties IRs. In essence, the Information Providers aka Lead Appointed Party is required to exchange the data deliverables with the Information Receiver aka Appointing Party, through filling in the 'openings', as seen in Figure 6 below (UK BIM Framework 2021):

Figure 6 - Information Requirements skeleton, Guidance Part D (UK BIM Framework, 2021)

ISO 19650-2 (2018) indicates that the IR documents must be established prior to invitation to tender, as the set of IRs should serve during the appointment process, so that prospective Lead Appointed Parties are fully aware and are contractually obliged to meet the IRs from the outset of a project. To contemplate, well-defined set of IR documents are to inform about the following (UK BIM Framework, 2021):

- the tendering and appointment process
- information delivery planning
- information generation and delivery
- the authorization and acceptance process by comparing deliverables against requirements
- the appropriate use of the information

It is recognised that set of IR documents is significant and in effect, the Appointing Party is required to be experienced enough or appoint competent organisation/individual to recognise the main purpose of requiring any information during the project delivery. As purely after understanding what, when, how and for whom these IRs are, these ought to be then seemingly draughted, communicated and included at the outset of a project, in order for the set of IRs to be contractually bounding with the Lead Appointed Party, so that all parts of IR are fully satisfied and delivered at each ie with the main outcome of achieving successful FM during O&M phase.

1.1.3 Facilities Management (FM)

According to TargetJobs (2021) Facilities Management (FM) ensure that a facility/assets perform smoothly throughout its operational life and that in essence occupants are satisfied. FM includes multiple disciplines with the aim of ensuring optimal functionality of the facility/assets (TargetJobs, 2021). According to Kelly (2018), FM's aim is to integrate people, places, processes, and technologies, which should cover all basic activities from day-to-day operation of a built environment e.g.: Asset Management (AM), Budget Management, Space Management, Maintenance, Cleaning, Testing, & Inspection, Refurbishment, Retrofitting, & Renovation, Sustainability, Regulatory Compliance and Safety & Security and many more (Neenu, 2020). Moreover, Facilities Managers also assess what is required within the facility and ensure that all legal requirements are adhered to as well as ensuring a regular maintenance check plan is in place (Bellrock, 2019).

As demonstrated above, FM is a very meaningful function at every facility, whether it is a small or large building as nobody takes pleasure in having issues with high cost of operations that lead to overheating or air quality. Extending the life of assets and the building itself is the biggest accomplishment that the Facilities Owners would dream of. Therefore, why would the Owners not like to take FM to the next level and improve their Building's efficiency or use the data for future refurbishment projects with the aid of BIM?

1.1.4 Building Information Modelling (BIM)

In accordance with the UK GOV (2016) Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a collaborative way of working, underpinned by the digital technologies, which unlock more efficient methods of designing, constructing, maintaining, and operating facilities/assets/infrastructure. The implementation of BIM across Government projects, from delivery through operational handover is facilitated by the adoption of Government Soft Landings (GSL) (IPA GOV, 2021). For that reason, BIM is genuinely the first global digital construction technology, which will be eventually deployed in every country in the world (UK GOV, 2012). Davidson (2022) further explains that it is achievable to develop, visualise, exchange, assure and subsequently use and re-use information to form reliable basis for decision-making to the benefit during asset's lifecycle through BIM, which is a consolidation of processes, standards, and not solely technologies.

BIM is not entirely a 3D modelling technology, which many think start at RIBA Stage 3, but to surprise of some BIM starts as soon as the Appointing Party decides to construct a building, therefore, in an ideal case scenario BIM commences at RIBA Stage 0. Even though BIM is heavily reliant on 3D technologies and allows for seamless production of data, more importantly the processes of collaboration, management, and planning, as well as latest Industry standards and policies should not be forgotten, as the combination of technologies, standards and processes will in essence profit the whole lifecycle of a facility/assets from BIM implementation.

1.1.5 UK GOV BIM Mandate

The UK Government decided to take a programme of measures to reduce costs and make the construction sector more efficient following the Government Construction Strategy in 2011. For that reason, under Government Construction Strategy (GCS) 2011-2015 the UK GOV set out its requirement for fully collaborative 3D BIM on centrally procured government construction projects, with BIM Level 2 being emerged to meet this mandate (UK GOV, 2016). In line with the ‘mobilisation and implementation’ plans contained in the follow-up BIM strategy in 2016, the use of BIM across centrally procured public construction projects was finally mandated in April 2016 (UK GOV, 2016). Even though, the UK GOV BIM Level 2 Mandate for the use of BIM was implemented in 2016, it was then superseded by the UK BIM Framework in 2018 (IPA GOV, 2021) and officially withdrawn on 18th August 2021 (UK GOV, 2021). Along with it, a new ‘Infrastructure & Projects Authority (IPA) 2030 Roadmap’ mandate was published on the 13th September 2021, which sets out a vision for innovation and transformation in projects delivery (IPA GOV, 2021). Government Soft Landings (GSL) was also integrated within the BIM mandate and aims to consider the whole lifecycle of the asset during the design and construction to achieve better outcomes through BIM during all RIBA Stages (Kelly, 2018).

Currently, BIM is based on the developing BS EN ISO 19650 suite of standards and any ‘not yet superseded’ BS/PAS 1192 suite of standards, with this new ‘IPA 2030 Roadmap’ including mandates for the following (IPA GOV, 2021):

- **‘Digital Twin Mandate’** = to enable the tracing of data and digital assurance throughout the process, with feedback on performance in use during the facility lifecycle
- **‘Information Management Mandate’** = to improve interoperability
- **‘Construction Platform approaches for relevant assets Mandate’** = so that assets in operation are tested from the outset

According to BSI (2022), BIM compliance in 2022 would be achieved with adhering to the following Standards shown in table 3, which are required to be written into the IRs at the outset of a project and agreed within project BEP. Table 3 is listing both latest standards and their withdrawn equivalent if there were any previously as shown below:

CURRENT BIM/IT STANDARDS	WITHDRAWN SUITE OF BIM LEVEL 2 STANDARDS	WHAT IT COVERS?
BS EN 17412-1:2020	<i>n/a</i>	BIM. Level of Information need - Concepts and principles.
PD 19650-0:2019	<i>n/a</i>	Transitional guidance to BS EN ISO 19650.
BS EN ISO 19650-1:2018	<i>PAS 1192-2:2013 / BS 1192:2007+A2:2016</i>	IM using BIM - Concepts and principles.
BS EN ISO 19650-2:2018	<i>PAS 1192-2:2013 / BS 1192:2007+A2:2016</i>	IM using BIM - Delivery phase of the assets.
BS EN ISO 19650-3:2020	<i>PAS 1192-3:2014</i>	IM using BIM - Operational phase of the asset.
BS EN ISO 19650-4 (TBC)	<i>BS 1192-4:2014</i>	Fulfilling EIR’s ie using COBie. - Delivering non-geometrical asset data.
BS EN ISO 19650-5:2020	<i>PAS 1192-5:2015</i>	IM using BIM - Security-minded approach to information management.
PAS 1192-6:2018	<i>n/a</i>	Collaborative sharing and use of structured Health and Safety information using BIM.
BS 8536:2022	<i>BS 8536-1:2015 / BS 8536-2:2016</i>	Design, manufacture, and construction for operability.

BS 8541-1:2012	<i>n/a</i>	Library objects for AEC - Identification and classification.
BS 8541-2:2011	<i>n/a</i>	Library objects for AEC - 2D symbols in BIM.
BS 8541-3:2012	<i>n/a</i>	Library objects for AEC - Shape and measurement.
BS 8541-4:2012	<i>n/a</i>	Library objects for AEC - Attributes for specification and assessment.
BS 8541-5:2015	<i>n/a</i>	Library objects for AEC – Assemblies.
BS 8541-6:2015	<i>n/a</i>	Library objects for AEC - Product and facility declarations.
PD ISO/TS 12911:2012	<i>n/a</i>	Framework for BIM guidance.
Information protocol	<i>CIC BIM Protocol:2018</i>	Legal agreement - common addendum to appointment document.
BS EN ISO/IEC 27000:2020	<i>BS EN ISO/IEC 27000:2017</i>	IT - Security techniques. Information security management systems.
Uniclass 2015	<i>Uniclass2</i>	Unified classification system.
<i>(TBC)</i>	<i>The NBS BIM Toolkit</i>	Management & validation of responsibility for information development and delivery.
RIBA Plan of Work 2020	<i>RIBA Plan of Work 2013</i>	Establishment of the process of briefing, designing, constructing, and operating building projects into 8 stages.

Table 3 – List of current & superseded BIM Standards (BSI, 2022)

Moreover, as equally as with the issue of new ISO standards the UK BIM Level 2 diagram was also updated to reflect more widely recognised representation of the IM maturity (PD 19650-0, 2019), which is interpreted into stages rather than levels as simplified in table 4 below. Table 4 and the new transition document called PD 19650-0:2019 are hopefully going to increase the understanding and general awareness of new BIM/IM maturity stages:

CURRENT STAGES	WITHDRAWN LEVELS	WHAT DOES IT INCLUDE?
STAGE 1	LEVEL 0	Digitally enabled processes; Structured & unstructured data; File/Model/Container & IM + CDE; National Standards;
STAGE 2	LEVEL 1	Digitally enabled processes; Structured & unstructured data + Federated Information Models; File/Model/Container & IM + CDE; ISO BS EN 19650 suite of Standards + Annexes;
STAGE 2	LEVEL 2	Digitally enabled processes; Structured & unstructured data + Federated Information Models; File/Model/Container & IM + CDE; ISO BS EN 19650 suite of Standards + Annexes;
STAGE 3	LEVEL 3	Digitally enabled processes; Structured & unstructured (BIG) data + Federated Information Models + Object based server Information Models; Query/Model/Container/Database & IM + CDE; Processes & Standards are yet to be developed;

Table 4 – Maturity stages (PD 19650-0, 2019)

Since the BIM standards along with the Stage 2 Maturity increase consistency that could be achieved on projects, it is not surprising that the UK Government decided to mandate their use since 2016 to improve collaboration, traceability, FM and interoperability on all Publically procured projects.

1.2 Research Methodology

Chapter 1.2 discusses how the aim and objectives of this research are being fulfilled, where mixed methods are adapted including both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. The quantitative methodology includes a literature review from books, journal papers, organisational research, development reports, documents, educational articles, and UK Government strategy documents that are publicly available to establish high-reliability standard sources with regards to BIM, FM and IRs. Whereas a pragmatic qualitative methodology includes a case study carried out on a live NMIS project at RIBA Stage 5. This means that all information is collected either from the Lead Appointed Party or Appointing Party via e-mails and meetings, to essentially examine Appointing Party's IRs, BEPs and Lead Appointed Party's BIM deliverables.

To answer the research questions, in first instance the Literature review forms basis to existing research to support the Level 1 & Level 2 analyses. Secondly, the Level 1 analysis assists to conclude, whether the Appointing Party's IR documents were clearly defined and were in fact included within the appointment suite of documents to utilise the Lead Appointed Party's BIM deliverables post-handover for O&M purposes. Further Level 1 analysis include an assessment of Pre-appointment BEP vs Post-appointment BEP, as well as retrospective observations & investigations to produce a clear understanding of whether the Post-appointment BEP contain sufficient details to support the delivery of NMIS project in alignment with Appointing Party's expectations. Moreover, Level 2 analysis focuses on interrogating MEP Information model in .RVT/.IFC formats, Federated Cobie Data Sheet, and Maintainable Asset List (MAL) that were agreed, implemented and published as part of the Lead Appointed Party's BIM deliverables mid RIBA Stage 5. These audits will form foundations on whether the BIM deliverables comply with Post-appointment BEP and/or Appointing Party's IR.

1.2.1 What did these methods allow to achieve?

Appointing Party's & Lead Appointed Party's BIM deliverables on the NMIS project are being analysed individually and findings from those analyses are populated within clear tables, showcasing alignment to each other and/or BIM Standards to identify gaps in relation to BIM & FM.

1.2.2 Benefits of using this methodology

This mixed research methodology appears to be objective, and these types of analyses enabled to capture real data based on observations and thorough investigations. Moreover, some level 2 analysis allowed for speedier analysis due to Revit software program when analysing the data, which measured the relationship between BEP content and Information Model rapidly.

1.2.3 Considerations and measures for Data protection

Both MCL and UoS have given consent to process collected BIM deliverables from the NMIS project for gap analysis purposes in this research. Moreover, the research endeavours to work with organisation's names or distinct BIM functions rather than stipulate any individuals' names. Lastly, as part of security measures, no specific information about the NMIS project regarding coordinates, secure assets, building layouts as well as personal data is unveiled in this research for liability purposes.

1.3 Research Limitations

First of all, the predominant limitation of this study was due to the fact that the Appointing Party has never produced their IRs, and for that reason, the Level 1 analysis were mostly illustrating the situation on the NMIS project rather than analysing the BEPs in response to IRs as initially desired.

Moreover, as a result of the construction works of the NMIS project being slightly delayed, the timing of research with the deadline of the research allowed for the gap analysis of WIP BIM deliverables to be carried out mid-through RIBA Stage 5, rather than at a typical end of stage to assist handing over of information to the Appointing Party, therefore, based on information available there might be more gaps in analysis than anticipated as the construction stage is not finalised yet.

Lastly, the longitudinal research was also unable to be undertaken due to time constraints.

1.4 Motivation to this Research

The motivation behind this research is the lack of awareness of what BIM, FM & IRs are, which relate to the knowledge gap on how and when IRs are required to be defined to implement BIM on projects in relation to FM deployment with regards to the latest suite of BS EN ISO 19650 Standards.

1.5 The aim of this Research

The aim of this research is to carry out an audit of Appointing Party's & Lead Appointed Party's BIM Deliverables on the NMIS project to identify gaps relating to BIM, FM & IRs, which will also fill the literature gap, whilst enabling to formulate a guidance for less experienced Appointing Parties & Appointed Parties on future projects. To achieve this aim, a set of objectives are set and listed below to ensure the success of this research investigation.

1.6 Objectives of the Research

1. To evaluate current literature review of BIM, FM & IRs
2. To compare Pre-appointment BEP vs Post- appointment BEP
3. To carry out gap analysis of BIM Deliverables on the NMIS project
4. To produce a guide to aid future BIM-enabled projects

1.7 Research Questions

1. Was there sufficient Information Requirements (IR) defined to utilise the Lead Appointed Party's BIM deliverables post-handover for Operation & Maintenance (O&M) purposes?
2. Were Information Requirements (IR) defined at the outset of a project and included within the HLM Architect's (HLM) & Morrison Construction (MCL) appointment suite of documents?
3. Does the Post-appointment BIM Execution Plan (BEP) contain sufficient details to support the delivery of BIM deliverables?
4. Has the MEP Information Model as well as COBie Data at RIBA Stage 5 been delivered in line with the Appointing Party's IRs and/or Post-appointment BEP?

1.8 Research Structure

Chapter 1.0 focuses on introducing the whole of research and the NMIS project as well as briefly explaining what IRs, FM, BIM and BIM mandate are. Furtherly it moves on to Methodology as well as its benefits, whilst examining considerations and measures for data protection. Moreover, it presents research limitations and what the writer got motivated by to carry out this case study, whilst presenting the aim with project objectives and finishing with research questions and research structure. Chapter 2.0 includes available literature review regarding more specific context of IRs, FM & BIM, whereas Chapter 3.0 completes gap analysis of the NMIS project and examines comparisons of BIM documents available on a project, whilst auditing BIM deliverables. The chapter ends with a guide to implement BIM for better FM on Publically procured projects. Moreover, chapter 4.0 discusses case study analyses, whilst identifying how aims, objectives & research questions are met. Finally, chapter 5.0 focuses on concluding the case study and recommending further research as well as proposing recommendations for future projects.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Chapter 2.0 is an overview of the key findings for this Literature Review research, which focuses on evaluating what has previously been established and argued in terms of interconnection between BIM, FM and most importantly IR suite of documents. The basis of this Literature Review will help with identifying the gaps in the analyses; therefore, the first sub-chapter 2.1 begins with demonstrating how BIM emerged in connection with FM, whilst swiftly moving on to chapter 2.2 that discusses the importance of early engagement of Facilities Managers to improve the O&M of the facility with the aid of BIM processes & technologies. Chapter 2.3 tabulates main challenges & benefits for Facilities Managers of BIM implementation for utilising Asset Information Model (AIM) and/or COBie Data beyond the Delivery Stage, whereas chapter 2.4 lists what key IR documents are conventionally required to be defined in alignment to BS EN ISO Standards. In addition, chapter 2.5 presents what BIM Deliverables are consistently required by Appointing Parties and/or by the UK BIM Mandate, while chapter 2.6 outlines the minimum requirements of the BEP. Lastly, chapter 2.7 explains different types of BIM audits, checks & validations that are typically required to be carried out by various project stakeholders during the project delivery.

2.1 Relationship between BIM, FM & AM

Asset Management (AM) is mostly associated with industrial settings, whereas, Facility Management (FM) is valuable in social housing, student halls, schools, hospitals, condominiums, and real estate as well as in businesses such as office buildings, hotels, accommodations, shopping centres and parks (InfraSpeak, 2021). According to ISO 55000 (2014) spanning the whole lifecycle of an asset / facility, AM is considered as coordinated activities of an organisation to appreciate value from assets. BIM, however, enables Information Management (IM) across all lifecycle stages in a structured and consistent way (PWC, 2020). For that reason, due to the long-life span of built assets/facilities, the O&M stage is frequently where most of the whole lifecycle cost is incurred, and therefore in use stage should represent a significant opportunity for cost efficiencies according to PWC (2020).

According to Stocks (2012) the construction industry is on a steep learning curve, but Stocks feels there is a willingness to engage and as the technologies become increasingly embedded, the industry's drive to embed them in all their activities such as planning, cost management, facilities management, reporting etc. will exponentially grow. Consequently, BIM presents opportunities for creation of company's wide standards to ensure consistent application across all planning, design and construction that aids O&M functions for Facility Managers (Shetty et al., 2014). The consistency might be especially crucial to be compatibly achieved on framework projects, where Appointing Party's circumstances allow for repeated work, as multiple buildings are either being newly developed or refurbished e.g. University buildings or Government offices etc.

Furthermore, PWC (2020) claims that BIM mandate focuses primarily on improving Information Management (IM) in the design and construction phases, with 1/3 of projects in the UK passing the Information models to those responsible for AM. However, BIM has an important application across the entire life cycle of assets/facility and is therefore a key enabler of improved AM & FM (Shetty et al., 2014). Building Information Modelling (BIM) nowadays is a highly important and integrated process in the AEC industry, which in first instance allows to view the progress of a project before and during design & construction (GlobalData, 2022), whilst eventually enhances the capability for Appointing Parties and their suppliers to develop and implement processes, tools and collaborative working practices to optimise asset costs and performance over the entire life cycle of facilities/assets (Shetty et al., 2014). For that reason, O'Rourke (2012) acknowledges the fact that BIM may maximise the value of the assets/facilities over their lifespan.

Subsequently, it is not very often that a word 'BIM' is being mentioned around FM, AM as well as Design for Manufacture and Assembly (DfMA), even though the UK's Government strategy documents have been revolving around those captions for over past 10 years. Having said that, BIM processes & technologies have not been seen to be used to its true potential, as BIM has been more noticeably used for Cost Management, Design, Planning & Construction, rather than for O&M beyond the delivery of a facilities/assets. The frameworks with properly set-up BIM standards, could benefit organisations to consistently progress with the individual project steps, from the outset to finalisation to achieve uniform results across all projects across the whole lifecycle in terms of FM & AM, but would early Facilities Managers engagement in the pre-appointment phase of a project, benefit organisations even more?

2.2 Facility Managers' engagement in the early phases of a project

According to SWG (2016) data stored within Information models may include schedules and blueprints as well as any required asset information such as cost, location, service life, carbon impact, maintenance, spares, re-ordering, substitution, serial number, warranty details and more. This is a staggering quantity of information, but when incorporated with a CAFM system, this information may be better managed by Facility Managers and be very effective indeed in maintaining the facility (SWG 2016).

Even though FM is during the Operation stage, Enoma (2006) considers that the input of FM is undoubtedly required at the design stage as minimum, and that Facility Managers should take more active part in project and the design. Facility Managers are, therefore, required to identify and translate the organisational objectives and requirement into forms that will meet the organisational needs by seeking to maximise performance of the facilities (Enoma 2006), which could be painlessly achieved by defining Asset Information Requirements (AIR) during or prior to the Concept Design Stage of any project to promote a consistent approach of O&M of facilities/assets. For that reason, Facility Managers ought to engage early in the project to develop appropriate Appointing Party's Information Requirements (IR) for BIM, FM and AM and communicate these to the Lead Appointed Party (Shetty et al., 2014) during or prior to tendering process. Considering FM at the early design stage would potentially reduce the efforts for maintenance during the operational phase of facilities (Wang et al., 2013). Unfortunately, it is still uncommon to see Facility Managers to be involved at those early design stages of projects, but Wang et al. (2013) state that BIM was envisaged to fill this gap by acting as a visual model and a database throughout the building lifecycle. Lastly, Keen (2018) identified that FM sector has had its struggles to get involved at the beginning of construction projects as Construction and FM do not speak the same language, however, Keen (2018) also claims that in the recent years, RIBA PoW has acknowledged the positive impact of early engagement from FM commencing at RIBA Stage 0-Strategic Definition, however, the problem still revolves around lack of knowledge from Appointing Parties about BIM and Soft Landings.

Facility Managers as well as Appointing Parties are still not necessarily keen to understand the current BIM processes and learn new software, therefore, the knowledge gap remains in terms of how to use the Information models beyond the Delivery Stage. Unfortunately, BIM and RIBA PoW are still misunderstood and therefore not utilised to its full extent and perhaps identifying skills gap of Facilities Managers as well as potential benefits of BIM would aid the effective BIM Implementation during O&M.

2.3 Challenges & Benefits of BIM in FM

There are plenty of benefits, but also challenges that affect FM sector with utilising Asset Information Model (AIM) and/or COBie Data beyond the Delivery Stage. According to Schley, et al. (2013) BIM bridges the data gap between Architecture, Engineering & Construction (AEC) as well as the Owner aka Appointing Party. Even though BIM processes/technologies are currently very extensively used within the construction sector and BIM is an important factor in the FM sector as well, it is unfortunately often misunderstood (SWG, 2016). On paper, BIM supports a truly collaborative environment that should facilitate an automatic seamless data flow between all stakeholders during a whole lifecycle of the facility/assets, however, Matarneh, et al. (2018) perceive that even though standard data formats are capable of exchanging data, particularly the open Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) and COBie Data sheets, the information exchange (ie) process between AIM/COBie data and FM systems is not as straightforward. For that reason, the following 9 challenges of BIM implementation have been identified within the FM sector, which are listed within the table 5 below to present and summarise the barriers that Owners and Facilities Managers currently face:

	CHALLENGES	DESCRIPTION	REFERENCE
1.	Knowledge gap	FM/Owners are not sure about how BIM should be used for FM; Facility Managers lack BIM skills.	<i>(Naghshbandi, 2016); (Gerber, et al., 2012); (Williams, et al., 2014)</i>
2.	Unclear benefits of BIM	Facility managers require authentic evidence to endorse BIM to owners, and existing case studies are unreliable about opportunities, benefits and challenges; Moreover, most Facilities Managers are still unclear of BIM benefits in ongoing FM practices e.g. imprecise productivity gains, or benefits gained from reduced equipment failure etc.	<i>(Naghshbandi, 2016); (Gerber, et al., 2012); (Williams, et al., 2014)</i>
3.	No FM engagement in the early phases	If Facility Managers are not able to specify the required data early in the project, this results in a reactive approach rather than proactive.	<i>(Naghshbandi, 2016); (Schley, et al., 2013)</i>
4.	Time required to define FM requirements	There is a lot of work required to define the specific FM needs, so that models/dataset are prepared in line the FM requirements.	<i>(Gerber, et al., 2012)</i>
5.	Inaccurate & Incomplete Information	Inadequacy of MEP systems or Spaces occurs often on project, therefore, checklist to prevent these issues for designers as well as data validation in form of assurance are required	<i>(Naghshbandi, 2016); (Zadeh, et al., 2015)</i>
6.	Superfluous Information	The information required by each organisation for FM purposes varies so the filtration of unnecessary dataset is required to be done by Designers prior to Information Exchange (ie), as additional data might be tedious and overwhelming to utilise by Facility Managers.	<i>(Naghshbandi, 2016); (Mohanta & Das, 2016); (Matarneh, et al., 2018)</i>
7.	Determining how much data is required	Data/details should be defined as early as possible for the Information models/data to be valuable during O&M, however, on many projects e.g. University of Chicago, the Owner/Facility Manager had troubles with defining for Designers how much data and how detailed the data should be for FM.	<i>(Schley, et al., 2013)</i>
8.	Interoperability capability	Logical data exchange between Information models and facilities management systems is required to be introduced within each organisation as Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) model and COBie data spreadsheets do not seem to be always compatible	<i>(Naghshbandi, 2016); (Matarneh, et al. 2018); (Gerber, et al., 2012)</i>

		with FM systems, and Facilities Managers appear to be inputting data into FM systems manually, even though it should be automatically linked.	
9.	Implementation cost & training	New technologies & processes require urgent training to implement them properly; Unfortunately, organisations do not have adequate resources/funding available for BIM training and also there is no clear plan for training in place for Facilities Managers.	(<i>Mohanta & Das, 2016</i>); (<i>Ashworth, 2017</i>)

Table 5 – List of BIM implementation challenges

Moreover, since BIM holds real promise for creating value for owners and FM organizations, implementation of BIM throughout the design and construction stages in line with well-defined Appointing Party's IRs, provides an excellent opportunity for Facilities Managers to transfer the assets information suitably (Gerber, et al., 2012). Therefore, organisations who are truly interested in utilising Information models/COBie data beyond the delivery stage to automate their FM processes, should focus on having enough resources and time to investigate the possible implementation areas as well as study those processes and identify possible benefits, and provide training to Facilities Managers and any additional personnel required (Gerber, et al., 2012). The following 7 benefits of BIM implementation within FM sector have been established and listed within the table 6 below to show what real value BIM would bring:

	BENEFITS	DESCRIPTION	REFERENCE
1.	Avoiding maintenance problems	If Facilities Manager are involved during early design stages, subsequently FM could influence the design early on and avoid maintenance problems.	(<i>Farman, 2012</i>)
2.	Cheaper & easier maintenance	If valuable asset history, information, and lifecycle costs are included within Information Models/COBie data, maintenance strategy would be easily changed thanks to BIM.	(<i>Walpole, 2012</i>)
3.	Time saving	6D Information models for FM could lead to a timesaving of up to 80% in operations and maintenance activities during the whole lifecycle of a facility e.g. to address equipment problems.	(<i>Naghshbandi, 2016</i>); (<i>Schley, et al., 2013</i>)
4.	Reduced cost	Developing CMMS, CAFM and BAS systems with the aid of BIM reduces FM costs & time.	(<i>Schley, et al., 2013</i>)
5.	Improved data quality	Quality of data with the aid of BIM in FM systems is better so that paper files are no longer required.	(<i>Schley, et al., 2013</i>)
6.	Better performance	BIM could enhance overall sustainability of the facility/assets including energy use, lifecycle costs, durability as well as reliability.	(<i>Schley, et al., 2013</i>); (<i>Mohanta & Das, 2016</i>);
7.	Integrated systems	Data from Information Models/COBie Data would be automatically incorporated into CAFM/CMMS/BAS systems, and effortlessly updated during the lifecycle of the facility/assets e.g. refurbishment.	(<i>Schley, et al., 2013</i>)

Table 6 – List of BIM implementation benefits

In a perfect scenario, accurate datasets in line with Asset Information Requirements (AIR) are expected to be delivered during handover of a project to support FM processes efficiently in fulfilling the organizational goals, however, in real world this does not happen very often. According to both table 5 with challenges & table 6 with benefits, first off, all attracted organisations to utilising BIM processes/technologies ought to require funding for any professional BIM training for all their essential personnel. Then once Facilities Managers are properly trained in utilising AIM/COBie Data during O&M, a consistent AIR is required to be created with the aid of Facilities Managers to support the whole lifecycle of their new facilities/assets. The IRs ought to be undoubtedly defined and detail

the information required, but also to list out details that are not needed to avoid inaccurate, incomplete & trivial information being delivered by Designers/Contractor at handover. Subsequently, the Facilities Managers are expected to be involved in the pre-appointment activities of the project to avoid maintenance problems down the line as well as bypass any interoperability issues, which leads to automatic linking of precise AIM/COBie data to FM Systems. Following the above should practically drive time & cost reduction as well as boost facility/assets performance and information quality for more economical & effortless O&M during the whole lifecycle, in addition to the suite of IRs being ideally defined within the tender documents at the outset of a project.

2.4 IR documents to be included at the outset of a project

According to Kornienko (2020), gathering and defining requirements is a fundamental part of any project. Therefore, to streamline the production of the Project Information Model (PIM) for Collaboration/Coordination/Construction purposes & then essentially Asset Information Model (AIM) for FM purposes, BS EN ISO 19650 suite of standards, calls for and represent 5 x documents aka suite of IRs to be produced by the Appointing Party as listed in table 7 below, whereas less experienced Appointing Parties might seek expert assistance to help with creating those IRs (BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018):

	SUITE OF IRs	DESCRIPTION	DETAIL
1.	Organisational Information Requirements (OIR)	organisational objectives	<i>high level IR</i>
2.	Asset Information Requirements (AIR)	operation & maintenance of an asset	<i>detailed IR</i>
3.	Project Information Requirements (PIR)	purpose, design, & construction of an asset	<i>high level IR</i>
4.	Security Information Requirements (SIR)	where applicable – in relation to information security	<i>detailed IR</i>
5.	Employer’s Information Requirements (EIR)	in relation to an appointment	<i>detailed IR</i>

Table 7 – List of required IR documents to be established (BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018) & (BS EN ISO 19650-3, 2018)

In addition, both BS EN ISO 19650-2:2018 and BS EN ISO 19650-3:2020 require that the Appointing Party establishes the following document listed in table 8, which is required to form part of tender and appointment documents (UK BIM Framework, 2021) so that the Lead Appointed Party is respectively obliged to comply with the Appointing Party’s IP, which is a code of contractual conduct to deal with risk allocation, setting out the rights and roles/responsibilities of the parties (Glover and Elliott, 2020):

	DOCUMENTS AS PART OF IRs	DESCRIPTION
6.	Information Protocol (IP)	means of capturing requirements into appointments

Table 8 – Protocol to be included as part of Suite of IRs at Tender (BS EN ISO 19650-2, 2018) & (BS EN ISO 19650-3, 2018)

Occasionally, as seen in the construction industry those 5 x IR documents do not necessarily contain all the information required for project delivery and separate documents are sometimes produced by the Appointing Parties and have been seen as shown in table 9 below:

	DOCUMENTS AS PART OF IRs	DESCRIPTION
7.	Naming Container Convention	definition of specific naming conventions of Rooms, Objects, Files, Parameters etc.
8.	Asset Delivery Requirements (ADR)	or separate documents (these are also sometimes seen to be included as part of the AIR):
8-a.	Maintainable Asset List (MAL)	schedule of maintainable objects paramount for operation & management
8-b.	Level of Information Need	description for information to be exchanged
8-c.	COBie Schema (COBie Demand Matrix)	definition of the LOI required for COBie format
8-d.	Responsibilities Matrix (RACI)	IM Assignment

Table 9 – other documents to be included as part of Suite of IRs (BS EN ISO 19650-2, 2018) & (BS EN ISO 19650-3, 2018)

Unfortunately, there is still a gap in accurately defining and including set of IRs in the appointment documents, which is caused by the obstacles of the Appointing Parties not being able to define details of quality management process tasks, hence there are no corresponding references within the appointment documents to be used for outlining quality control items over the Information model's content (Leygonie, et al., 2021). According to Fugas (2021), the Appointing Party should define and require within their set of IRs the indispensable information, in relation to both Level of

Information Need and Scope. Concurrently the Appointing Party ought not to define information within the set of IRs for the Delivery Team to drive that process, claims Fugas (2021). Also, Fugas (2021) notes that if an Appointing Party operates a framework of projects e.g. NHS or MoJ, it is advisable to rationalize these documents so they consistently fit any future activities. Unfortunately, in a typical scenario where set of IRs is not defined, there is no formal agreement in place between the Delivery Team and the Appointing Party with regards to PIM/AIM and other deliverables, which leads further down the line to no understanding of what information is needed, which creates failed attempts to plan how any information on a project will be delivered, what timescales are required, including any commitment of resources (UK BIM Framework, 2021).

Both part 1 & part 2 of BS EN ISO 19650 suite of standards precisely detail how all 5 x IR documents should be established and enlists how and what ought not be included in each and one of them. For that reason, if the instructions set within those standards are precisely followed, these should be an excellent starting point for any organisation to define their requirements for information either for a single project or for a framework of projects. As such, including IR documents at the outset of a project may seem like a hassle for Appointing Parties, as these need to be well-defined at a very early stage of a project, where some of the items might simply be unknown. However, even determining all those items as defined within part 1 & part 2 of BS EN ISO 19650 suite of standards, which are yet unknown and stating that these will be detailed and communicated to the Lead Appointed Party later on in a project, would secure each appointing organisation. This in essence will lead to including all essential areas in the appointment documents to avoid the change of cost or time of the project delivery. For that reason, a well-defined suite of IRs is particularly important with regards to BIM Deliverables required at every Information Exchange (ie), since this is what the Appointing Party will be accepting and fundamentally utilising during O&M stage.

2.5 Typical Lead Appointed Party's BIM Deliverables at ie

According to BS EN ISO 19650-1 (2018) an act of satisfying IRs is called information exchange (ie). Successful part of each ie for every BIM deliverable according to the UK BIM Framework (2020) is the level of information need, which due to its definition being often too generic is unfortunately most of the time open to interpretation, and that increases project risks and wasteful production of information. Level of information need is typically defined at the beginning of each appointment within the AIR to specify the quality, quantity, and granularity of information the Facilities Manager requires (UK BIM Framework, 2020). The main intention for each ie is to provide all the significant information that Facility Managers require to operate and maintain their facilities (Lewis, 2012) aligned at each project milestone, which shall be aligned with the Government Soft Landings (GSL) processes. GSL drives a structured and consistent approach to the delivery of facilities/infrastructure by focussing on early FM engagement and O&M requirements from the outset of a project (IPA GOV, 2021). IPA GOV (2021) also claims that GSL in essence allows the early testing of maintainability and performance targets as the design progresses at each ie. Unfortunately, there might be potential risks with the interoperability of each ie, however, Kassem and Dawood (2014) recommend emerging a BIM technological diagram based on BIM tools' functions and to link these functions to the project deliverables required at every RIBA PoW Stage. Moreover, defining BIM deliverables is still deemed challenging for the Appointing Parties/Facilities Managers, which according to Leygonie, et al. (2021) might be due to the limited knowledge of BIM data within Information models, which makes it difficult to identify requirements related to the consistency and completeness of the Information models, even though Appointing Parties and Facilities Managers are familiar with the types of information required for their O&M platforms.

According to Kemp (2015), as a means to understand how to define the set of IRs and deliverables for the Appointing Party, it is essential to understand where the real value and the long-term return on investment in BIM is. Surprisingly, there is a variety of deliverables that might be required, which is purely dependant on the IRs, project scope or Employer's Requirements (ER) of a project. With regards to BIM, BS EN ISO 19650-1 (2018) defines 'Information deliverables' as model files, documents and data files. However, according to Shahrudin and Zairul (2020) COBie data seems to be the main BIM deliverable in compliance with BIM Mandate, but some organisations ask for an AIM as a substitution to the COBIE deliverables. Moreover, BIM deliverables are normally first collated by the Lead appointed party before the official delivery to the Appointing Party through each ie (BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018). According to BS EN ISO 19650-1 (2018) an Information Management (IM) process does not entirely involve preparation of IR and the review of prospective appointed parties regarding IM function, but also includes comprehensive planning for how and when information is delivered, as well as reviewing the BIM deliverables against the IR before they are integrated with Appointing Party's O&M systems. Nevertheless, typical 'BIM deliverables', not solely requests 'information' within the IR, but actually calls for specific items and explicit formats of 'BIM deliverables' required in line with BIM mandate at each ie mapped with RIBA PoW Stages as listed in table 10 below, rather than just focusing on information itself:

	BIM DELIVERABLE	WHEN	WHY	REFERENCE
1.	Compliance with IR	at all RIBA Stages	to avoid delivery of incorrect information of a facility/assets to an Appointing Party during each ie, but specifically a handover stage.	(NBS, 2016) (Shahrudin and Zairul, 2020)
2.	Common Data Environment (CDE)	at all RIBA Stages	to support the collaborative production of information in a secure single source of truth throughout the life of the project delivery and asset management with the use of workflows and information containers	(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018); (NBS, 2016) (UK BIM Framework, 2021)

			to ensure that information is carefully planned, shared, stored, managed and retrieved, which in essence is timely, correct, complete, and consistent. This is to maintain the audit trail of information handling.	<i>(UK BIM Framework, 2020)</i>
3.	Naming Convention	at RIBA Stage 1 or 2	to agree and adopt a consistent naming of information containers for files, assets, spaces etc. to help plan the production of information by separate task teams. In terms of CDE, naming convention will also enable each information container to have a unique ID.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018); (BS EN ISO 19650-2, 2018);</i>
4.	3D BIM Survey	at RIBA Stage 2	to capture reality and manage existing digital data of site and/or existing facility/assets.	<i>(NBS, 2016) (King, 2021)</i>
5.	Capability & Capacity Assessment	at each appointment (e.g. RIBA Stage 2 & 4)	to determine whether the Lead Appointed Party is competent to deliver IR as well as to assess if the Delivery Team is able to perform and complete BIM activities in the required time e.g. by having the fundamental experience, skill or technical resources.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018); (UK BIM Framework, 2021)</i>
6.	BIM Execution Plan (BEP)	at RIBA Stages 2 to 4	to plan and organize the work, mobilize the right resources, coordinate, and control development that reflects what the delivery team as a whole will do in line with the set of IR (<i>Pre-appointment and Post-appointment BEPs</i>).	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018); (NBS, 2016); (UK BIM Framework, 2021)</i>
7.	Responsibility Matrix (RM)	at RIBA Stages 2 to 4	to finalise the appointment as an Appointed party/Task team, and indicate responsibility, accountability, consultation and informing to complete tasks or deliverables.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018); (UK BIM Framework, 2021)</i>
8.	Master Information Delivery Plan (MIDP)	at RIBA Stages 2 to 5	to compile all the Task Information Delivery Plans (TIDPs) into MIDP to baseline the deliverables & dates and make sure those deliverables fit with the Delivery Team schedule of activities.	<i>(UK BIM Framework, 2021); (UK BIM Framework, 2020)</i>
9.	COBie Data	at RIBA Stages 2 to 5	to fulfil ie requirements using COBie as part of the National BIM Standard, which should be integral to the whole Facility lifecycle that ought to be progressively more complete at each ie throughout the RIBA Stages, culminating at the handover into 'operation' to manage asset information including space, equipment, systems and more.	<i>(Lewis, 2012); (NBS, 2016); (IStrucE, 2021); (BS 1192-4, 2014)</i>
10.	Unfederated – 3D discipline Models	at RIBA Stages 2 to 5	to improve collaboration, design, operation cost & clashes by delivering geometrical and non-geometrical data of each core discipline, including:	<i>(NBS, 2016) (IStrucE, 2021)</i>

			Architectural, MEP and Structural/Civil using 3D BIM supported software.	
11.	Federated - Project Information Model (PIM)	at RIBA Stages 2 to 5	to support the delivery phase of a project whilst reducing risk & cost by federating all discipline information models into a federated one to achieve a virtual representation of the asset to be constructed, which contributes to the AIM to support asset management activities.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018)</i> <i>(NBS, 2016)</i>
12.	2D Drawings – exported from Information Model	at RIBA Stages 2 to 5	to output 2D layouts into PDF/CAD format directly from each Information model, as traditional drawings on paper or in a tablet are still required.	<i>(Kjartansdóttir, et al., 2017);</i> <i>(UK BIM Framework, 2020)</i>
13.	Spatial Coordination (Clash Detection reports)	at RIBA Stages 3 to 5	as part of Collaborative production of information to achieve Constructability & Spatial Coordination with the help of collaboration software and regular coordination meetings to resolve any spatial issues and speed projects in identifying clashes between numerous discipline Information models prior to construction.	<i>(Kendrick, 2019);</i> <i>(NBS, 2016);</i> <i>(UK BIM Framework, 2020)</i>
14.	Classifications	at RIBA Stages 3 to 5	to classify the information containers during the CDE workflow as well as to support the object exchange within Information models with e.g. Uniclass 2015, NRM 1, NRM 3, SFG20 classification etc. to achieve consistent arrangement of information, cost management and maintenance.	<i>(NBS, 2016);</i> <i>(UK BIM Framework, 2020);</i> <i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018)</i>
15.	Federated - Asset Information Model (AIM)	at RIBA Stage 6 to 7	to transfer structured and unstructured information from PIM to AIM during handover for storing all accepted information during O&M phase, which could contain equipment registers, cumulative maintenance costs, records of installation and other details that the Appointing Party regards as valuable.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018)</i> <i>(NBS, 2016)</i>

Table 10 – List of typical BIM Deliverables + when & why they are required

Nevertheless, there is a variety of BIM deliverables desired on projects and these are completely dependent on Appointing Party's devotion out of projects at each ie, with the end result in mind being the biggest benefit for the O&M purposes to perhaps align any formats and items of BIM deliverables with current organisational FM practices or aspirational future goals and objectives. Moreover, in terms of privately procured projects, the list in table 10 of BIM deliverables might be too exhaustive for privately owned organisations. Private sector in the UK is still not obliged to be adhering to any BIM mandates or specific standards, therefore, the BIM deliverables may extremely differ from those Publically procured projects as these need to align to BS/PAS/ISO Standards and the BIM mandate as well as the UK Strategy, whether they wish to and are experienced enough or not. However, private sector may be more interested in BIM-driven benefits and the list of BIM deliverables required could on the other hand end up being more intensive than in table 10.

Lastly, the list of typical BIM deliverables identified in table 10 is not exactly a list of ‘physical’ deliverables. BIM deliverables such as Compliance with IR, Naming Convention or Spatial Coordination between all the systems, felt plausible to include within table 10 of 15 x BIM deliverables, as they appeared to be the most significant ‘elements’ for Appointing Parties from the Public sector to wish to achieve and/or receive, which are also in line with the Standards and BIM Stage 2 requirements.

Lastly, the gap in research found with regards to BIM deliverables is around level of Information need, which due to its prior and current definition within BS/PAS & ISO Standards is unfortunately not easily understood by many. Even though, there has been a separate standard created called BS EN 17412-1:2020, each Appointing Party is recommended to exclusively interpret Level of Information need requirements within their set of IRs. Nonetheless, do the processes, management, and any further details of these BIM deliverables as well as execution of BIM throughout the project lifecycle require to be further defined apart from what is already included within the IRs?

2.6 BIM Execution Plan (BEP) content

According to BS EN ISO 19650-2 (2018) a BEP is a comprehensive plan that explains how the Information Management (IM) conditions of the appointment are to be approached by the delivery team in response to IRs, which essentially helps all project stakeholders move forward from the beginning of any construction project with clear roles and expectations of all individuals, teams, and organizations (Ramage 2022). According to GSA (n.d.n.) the success of a project relies on defining precisely planning of the design-to-engineering-to-construction processes, which are crucial to decrease any subsequent surprises, rework, redundancies, or even gaps in the flow of information. However, UK BIM Framework (2020) identified another purpose of the BEP, which provides a delivery tool that the appointed delivery team will use to produce, manage, and exchange project information beside other resources. GSA (n.d.n.) also draws the attention to making sure a BIM Kick-off Meeting is programmed to review the submitted BEP with all stakeholders, including all BIM members and reviewers to ensure everybody agrees with the established plan.

Nevertheless, Ramage (2022) identified two types of BEPs as follow:

- **Pre-appointment BEP**
- **Post-appointment BEP**

However, according to the UK BIM Framework (2020) there might be multiple pre/post-appointment BEPs created on one project that indicates different nature of the appointments, e.g. if different Lead Appointed Parties get appointed for different scope of services at various RIBA Stages, then this scenario requires BEP activities to be restated.

Even though both BEPs might enclose of similar content, they both serve slightly different purposes. Once the suite of IRs is incorporated into the tender documentation, this in first instance enables the Lead Appointed Party to produce a pre-appointment BEP upon which their proposed approach, capability and capacity must be evaluated to meet the Appointing Party's IRs (BS PAS 1192-2, 2013). The Pre-appointment BEP, which is quite high-level at this point is then required to be returned with other tender response documents (BIM Framework 2020). Whereas the Post-appointment BEP is subsequently re-submitted with more details following the Tender award, demonstrating that appointed parties have agreed and committed to that BEP (SFT, n.d.n.).

For that reason, the content of every BEP will be slightly different but should as minimum consist of the response of everything as requested within the suite of IRs with clear approach and definition (BS PAS 1192-2, 2013). The UK BIM Framework (2020) explains that in circumstances that there is no suite of IR documents available on a project, each prospective Lead Appointed Party must respond with a Pre-appointment BEP in accordance with BS EN ISO 19650-2 standard in anticipation of the IRs. Nonetheless, the UK BIM Framework (2020) recommends that BEP's content ought to be exclusively established in response to the Appointing Party's IRs included within the Tender documents, whilst acknowledging the following details as defined in table 11 below as per clause 5.3.2 within BS EN ISO 19650-2 (2018):

	BEP CONTENT	WHY IS IT REQUIRED?
A.	Details of individuals for IM functions	to provide assurance to the Appointing Party that the IM function will be fulfilled competently as well as providing details on how this function will be resourced.
B.	Information Delivery Strategy	Delivery Team's approach to work through and consider each IR including Level of information need, Acceptance criteria and Delivery dataset, whilst determining collaborative goals & objectives for the project, and examining Delivery Team's organisational structure, commercial relationships, and composition of each Task Team.

C.	Federation Strategy	to plan the production of information by each Task Team to the appropriate Level of Information Need at required RIBA stages, which is required to be done collaboratively.
D.	Responsibility Matrix (RM)	to allocate responsible parties for each of the Information Model elements and its deliverables.
E.	Information Production Methods & Procedures	to recommend any additional methods and procedures over what is currently specified or not by the Appointing Party, including simplified capture of current Asset Information, Approval & Authorisation, Security & Distribution as well as Delivery of that information.
F.	Project’s Information Standard	to propose amendments to Information Standard over what is currently specified or not by the Appointing Party, which comprises of Information Exchange (ie), Information Distribution and Information Delivery.
G.	Software, Hardware, and IT	to fundamentally consider and propose schedules listing the software versions, hardware, and IT to be used by the delivery team.

Table 11 – BEP’s list of content (UK BIM Framework, 2020) / (BS EN ISO 19650-2, 2018)

Unfortunately, it is very difficult to specify exact BEP’s content prior to reviewing Appointing Party’s IRs, and even though many organisations outline and rely heavily on their own ‘Organisational templates’, which might strive when there is no set of IRs created, but these templates will definitely need to be re-vamped for more experienced Appointing Parties who know exactly what they want. Consequently, no matter what content the BEP has, even if it includes everything and more as per table 11 shown above, the BEP will never be satisfying enough if it is not fully responding to the suite of IR documents. Specifically, if that BEP is a copy and paste of the Organisational Lead Appointing Party’s BEP template, which doubtfully will be answering accurately to what the Appointing Party wants, but rather dictating what the Appointing Party will get, which is not an ideal scenario. For that reason, the Appointing Party or an individual/organisation acting on behalf of the Appointing Party should audit and validate both Pre-appointment BEP and Post-appointment BEP to assure that the BEPs are following the IRs and are in accordance to agreed standards.

2.7 Types of BIM Reviews

According to Thomson (2019) BIM delivers quality assurances, therefore, Information at each ie is required to be fit for purpose. Since, IM is about making sure that the right information is delivered to the right destination at the right time to meet a specific purpose (UK BIM Framework, 2020), BIM Audits, Checks & Validations are carried out to provide assurance that the projects are performing as intended to conclude each ie. BS EN ISO 19650-1 (2018) illustrates validation methods to be vital for the approval and acceptance procedures, hence these should be agreed and documented before any ie occur. Additionally, where there is a change of Appointed party between one RIBA Stage and the next RIBA Stage or there is a programme delay, the usability of all Information received ought to be validated for the second time to progress to the next project stage (BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018).

To achieve successful delivery of a BIM project, QA & QC reviews specifically against IRs are required (UK BIM Framework, 2020). There is, however, a variety of BIM validation methods and audits currently being used/requested as part of the industry best practice, which are described in more detail within BS/PAS 1192 & BS EN ISO 19650 suite of standards, which are listed in table 12 below. Appointing Parties are, therefore, keener to get assurance that the information delivered is in fact QA checked as well as reviewed, prior to being further audited and authorised by the Appointing Parties themselves against their suite of IRs. Moreover, to make table 12 more straightforward to understand, it got segregated by responsibilities of 3 main parties as follow: Task Team, Lead Appointed Party and Appointing Party, which have been implied as responsible in BS/PAS & BS EN ISO Standards, but of course these responsibilities may vary on project's scope and capabilities of all Project Stakeholders, therefore, the appointments with regards to responsibilities may differ from what is shown below:

	TYPE OF BIM REVIEW	DESCRIPTION	REFERENCE
RESPONSIBILITY = APPOINTING PARTY OR DELEGATED COMPETENT INDIVIDUAL			
1.	Capability & Capacity Review	Review of Delivery Team's Capability and Capacity to manage information, to produce information, to work in a collaborative way, as well as availability of IT and experience within their organisations, whilst reviewing Delivery Team's commitment to comply with IRs in addition to checking all organisations' suitable resources, which should be concluded before the appointment is made.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018)</i>
2.	BIM Execution Plan Audit	Review & confirmation of the BEP against the IRs during the period between the appointment being indicated by the Appointing Party and the contract being signed, however, the BEP is a live document and ought to be updated throughout the appointment, using change management processes.	<i>(UK BIM Framework, 2020)</i>
3.	Information Model Audit	Audit of the Information Model in accordance with the IRs and acceptance criteria for each IR, BIM deliverables within MIDP and the Level of Information need for each IR, which may include items as follow: visual check, discrepancies, cleanliness, flying objects, spaces, view templates, systems, browser organisation, file naming, object naming, etc.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-2, 2018); (Techure, n.d.n.)</i>
4.	Project Information Model (PIM) Audit	Audit of the developed federated Information Models, which should be stored to provide a long-term archive of the project as PIM contain all combined geometrical and non-geometrical data.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018)</i>
5.	Asset Data Validation	Validation of asset information at each ie with feedback loops so that information deliverables are revised & re-submitted if required, this involves an Appointing Party's initiative in validating	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018)</i>

		information supplied from Appointed Parties, whilst eventually authorising all asset information for inclusion into the AIM, so that key information beeing handed over include information required for O&M of the facility/assets.	
RESPONSIBILITY = LEAD APPOINTED PARTY			
6.	Information Model Review	Review of the Information Model in accordance with the Project's Information Production Methods and Procedures against the IR and acceptance criteria as well as deliverables within the MIDP.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-2, 2018);</i>
7.	Information handling - Audit trail	Audit trail of Information development, where all information container transactions are to be archived providing a journal of all information handling.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018)</i>
RESPONSIBILITY = LEAD APPOINTED PARTY / TASK TEAM / LEAD DESIGNER			
8.	Coordination Review	Review of geometrical models to facilitate continuous coordination of Information to minimise issues such as: major unresolved clashes between systems, links not removed, shared coordinates, warnings, errors etc.	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-2, 2018); (Tecture, n.d.n.)</i>
RESPONSIBILITY = TASK TEAM			
9.	Quality Assurance (QA) Information Container Check	Check of each Information Container aka unique file ID, whether it is in compliance with the Project's Information Production Methods & Procedures as well as Project's Information Standard (this could be automated within the project CDE).	<i>(UK BIM Framework, 2020); (BS EN ISO 19650-2, 2018)</i>
10.	Availability of Reference Information & Shared Resources Check	Check whether there is access to Reference Information & Shared Resources provided by either the Appointing Party or Lead Appointed Party prior to any generation of Information commencement (it could never be shared).	<i>(UK BIM Framework, 2020); (BS EN ISO 19650-2, 2018)</i>
11.	Information Review	Review & Approval of the information for 'sharing' against the IRs, Level of Information Need as well as examine the Information needed for Coordination (typically in a form of checklist).	<i>(BS EN ISO 19650-2, 2018)</i>

Table 12 – Types of BIM Reviews

BIM reviews as listed in table 12 above including audits, checks, validations & verifications are extremely important as they are destined to eliminate errors during the lifecycle of a project/facility and certainly aid with achieving compliance against the suite of IRs, acceptance criteria, MIDP and Level of Information Need. For that reason, it is recommended that Appointing Parties follow BS EN ISO 19650 suite of standards, when creating/updating their IRs to achieve the most out of the QA/QC processes described, but also other fundamental BIM aspects for favourable project delivery.

2.8 Synthesis of the Literature Review

After a thorough review of the current Literature relating to BIM & FM, it appears that the previous research on related topics is robust as per this research, the relationship between BIM & FM as well as data requirements and challenges/benefits were analysed. However, the methods used e.g. interviews, may cause biased or fictitious information due to lack of understanding. Moreover, the literature is mainly identified in the UK or USA, however, there was also research done in other countries including Europe and Asia. The educational papers were frequently carrying the analysis via Interviews, Case studies or Reviews, whereas the articles were mostly based on Observations, Industry experience or Case studies. Even though there have been excellent guides produced that focus on implementing BIM by the UK BIM Framework, these would not be easy to comprehend by less experienced project stakeholders. Therefore, the current gap within the Literature seems to be the lack of best practice and easy to understand guidelines of implementing BIM for the whole lifecycle of a facility/infrastructure from the outset of a project continuously to O&M.

Nevertheless, having to synthesise all the literature reviewed, GlobalData (2022) identified that BIM is a highly important and integrated process in the AEC industry, which in first instance allows to view the progress of a project before and during design & construction. Having said that, BIM has been considered by many organisations as a ‘tool’ for better planning, design & delivery of a project, however, BIM is not being implemented for the sole reason of those, as identified in many previous research papers. In fact, FM is the biggest target for Appointing parties to implement BIM rather than just for design, which Shetty et al., (2014) genuinely confirms that BIM implementation is empowering the whole lifecycle of a facility/infrastructure. For that reason, as part of strong BIM foundations of a project, Facilities Managers should engage as early as possible to define IRs so that Appointing Party’s expectations are fully outlined in a standardised manner early on (Leygonie, et al., 2021). Even though, BIM seems to be bridging the data gap between Delivery Teams and Appointing Parties (Schley, et al., 2013), the processes & technologies between BIM, AIM, COBie data and FM systems are not so straightforward. Consequently, training must be mandatory to implement BIM properly, however since public organisations do not have adequate resources/funding available, there is still a huge gap in skills, for that reason the Government ought to introduce grants. Especially, that it has been 6 years since BIM has been mandated and there is still confusion around benefits of implementing BIM on projects. Despite the high costs, proper training would absolutely increase the basic knowledge of BIM, which would develop in highly considerable understanding, so that Facilities Managers would indeed engage in the early stages of projects and produce useful IRs to determine BIM deliverables required to avoid superfluous Information being delivered.

Furthermore, according to Kemp (2015), it is essential to understand where the real value and the long-term return on investment in BIM is, in terms of demanding specific BIM deliverables within the set of IRs by Facilities Managers. Since ‘BIM deliverables’, are not entirely about ‘information’, as the IRs should also call for specific activities and explicit formats of ‘BIM deliverables’ required in line with the BIM mandate. Identifying IRs related to the consistency & completeness, would in essence result in receiving BIM deliverables in the right format to O&M facilities (Lewis, 2012). Likewise, once the suite of IRs is incorporated into tender in response to IRs, a broad plan aka BEP is vital to be produced by the Lead Appointed Party. The BEP’s role is to interpret those IRs into what the appointed delivery team are required to produce, and how they are going to manage & exchange project information (UK BIM Framework, 2020). The content of the BEP is specifically important and ought to be exclusively established in response to IRs, whilst acknowledging standards. Subsequently, by BIM also driving better QA/QC, the data delivered is required to be fit for purpose (Thomson, 2019), for that reason a variety of BIM validation methods & audits are required as part of the industry best practice. The responsibility of carrying reviews depends on what has been defined within IRs and the BEP. Thus, gap analyses in this research include a varied audits on the NMIS project, which must be carried out on projects to improve the BIM deliverables transferred.

2.9 Summary

It has been established that there is an extensive connection between BIM, FM & AM, since BIM could maximise the value of the assets/facilities over their lifespan. For that reason, Facility Managers' engagement in the early phases of a project is found to be advantageous to identify and translate the objectives and requirements into IRs to maximise performance of the facilities as well as improve O&M. Even though, there have been more challenges than benefits found of implementing BIM for FM purposes, the technology and processes should be constantly improving the current industry practices. For that reason, it is believed that the government is overlooking the responsibility of training and if the government would like something new to be implemented, there ought to be adequate resources/funding available for appropriate training.

If training was implemented, consequently the IRs suite of documents would be perfectly defined and included within the appointment documents, for the BEP to be provided in response to those defined IRs. Following on, the BIM deliverables would be precisely delivered in the right format with the applicable LOI thanks to well established BEP and relevant BIM checks/audits being carried out throughout the duration of the project, so that BIM deliverables are fully fit for O&M principles.

3.0 GAP ANALYSES – NMIS PROJECT (Case Study)

Delivering a public project in 2022 is not a straightforward process, as the government requires buildings and infrastructures to be designed, delivered, maintained, and operated utilising BIM processes and technologies. For that reason, to implement BIM at different stages of a project and hand the project over with the required information against the set criteria by the Appointing Party, a number of Audits, Checks & Validations should be regularly carried out by Lead Appointed Party / Task Team / Lead Designer / Appointing Party or Delegated Competent Individuals commonly in the likes of Project Information Managers (IM), Task Team Information Manager (TIM), Task Team Interface Manager (ITM) and Employer's Information Managers (EIM).

Consequently, chapter 3.1 & chapter 3.2 consist of Level 1 gap analyses on the NMIS project, which validate and check the documents that are recommended to be included on public projects, whereas chapter 3.3 demonstrates Level 2 gap analyses of the MEP Information Model as well as COBie data sheet that ought to be produced in line with the project/framework IRs and in adherence to BS/PAS 1192 suite of Standards (previously) and nowadays to BS EN ISO 19650 suite of Standards as well as BEPs and MAL. These two deliverables selected are the most applicable for FM purposes, hence the reason for being analysed. Lastly, chapter 3.4 accomplishes the analysis with a basic guidance to conform to on future projects to achieve better results, which fills the gap in the Literature review.

Moreover, the terminology as well as analysis throughout this research are used as per latest suite of BS EN ISO 19650 Standards that were originated back in 2018 and officially published under the power of the Standards Policy and Strategy Committee on 31 January 2019. Nevertheless, the NMIS project was agreed to be delivered to the oldest suite of BS/PAS 1192 Standards, even though the project commenced following the issue of the latest ISO Standards, and the Planning Application for the NMIS project was submitted on 25.09.19 as identified within the Pre-appointment BEP.

3.1 Level 1 Analysis – Appointing Party's IRs

At the beginning of a project, the organisational stakeholders are required to collaborate efficiently to ensure that all the relevant IRs are defined. Regrettably, no typical IRs were draughted for the NMIS project nor they have been developed on Framework level for any UoS projects yet. Since, Appointing Party never issued any IR documents, project BIM objectives and goals have been set out by HLM within their pre-appointment BEP.

Furthermore, as explained at the meeting held on the 22.02.22 with Assistant Director Estates Development & Operations and the Project Manager – Capital Projects of the UoS on the NMIS project, Appointing Party had agreed to outsource FM. For that reason, Appointing Party explained that a consistent approach of delivering the BIM deliverables for FM purposes was never a priority. In addition, full potential of the operational 3D model is not seen imperative of replicating it consistently across other UoS' facilities, as other organisations will be managing UoS' facilities. Could perhaps the outsourced FM be dictating the IRs instead?

3.1.1 IRs included at the outset of a project

As disclosed by MCL, UoS engaged the Design teams providing an outline brief and from there the IRs were developed by HLM in a form of a pre-appointment BEP prior to the works coming out for tender. The design pack at tender also known as ‘works information’, which included drawings and complimenting specifications/reports issued by HLM Architects (HLM), McCulloch Service Engineers (DML) and Waterman Structures & Davie (WSL) were the exclusive documents agreed to be reflective of Appointing Party’s IRs.

Following tender award, MCL then disclosed that they have picked up the ‘works information’ and taken the design responsibility to develop this outline design into a construction status solution, which in effect means that ‘works information’ as well as the pre-appointment BEP were in turn the exclusive ‘IRs’ created for the NMIS project issued at tender, in addition to the ADR being produced by MCL post-appointment award, as shown in the table 13 below:

	IRs or DOCUMENTS AS PART OF SUITE OF IRs	BY WHOM	INCLUDED
REQUIRED AT THE OUTSET OF A PROJECT			
1.	Organisational Information Requirements (OIR)	UoS	NO
2.	Asset Information Requirements (AIR)	UoS	NO
3.	Project Information Requirements (PIR)	UoS	NO
4.	Security Information Requirements (SIR)	UoS	NO
5.	Employer’s Information Requirements (EIR)	UoS	NO
6.	Information Protocol (IP) / CIC Protocol	UoS/HLM/MCL	NO
7.	Naming Container Convention	UoS	NO
REQUIRED PRE or POST-APPOINTMENT			
8.	Asset Delivery Requirements (ADR):	UoS/HLM/MCL	YES
8-a.	Maintainable Asset List (MAL)	MCL	YES
8-b.	Level of Information Need (LoIN) = within pre-appointment BEP	HLM	YES
8-c.	COBie Schema (COBie Demand Matrix)	MCL	YES
8-d.	Responsibilities Matrix (RACI) = within post-appointment BEP	MCL	YES

Table 13 – Types of IRs included

Furthermore, MCL along with BSL produced a follow up post-appointment BEP to explain how the IM aspects of the appointment are approached by the delivery team in response to the pre-appointment BEP and ‘works information’. Accordingly, there should be no challenge to meet Appointing Party’s IRs as these are expected to be precisely interpreted within the pre-appointment BEP, hence the post-appointment BEP shall correspond in harmony to HLM’s pre-appointment BEP.

3.2 Level 1 Analysis – Appointed Party’s BIM Execution Plan (BEP)

Since the BEP details the project deliverables stipulated by the appointment and RIBA stages, both pre-appointment BEP and post-appointment BEP are bound to be listing different deliverables but should still be in response to Appointing Party’s IRs. Unfortunately, in absence of Appointing Party’s IR documents, HLM’s pre-appointment BEP and ‘works information’ takes precedence.

Consequently, both tables in chapters 3.2.1 and 3.2.2 analyses the details of the typical expected contents of the BEP established in BS EN ISO 19650 against what was produced within the pre-appointment BEP. The tables also include recommendations with what could be revised, whilst validating whether everything is included as per chapter 2.6 in the Literature review.

Chapter 3.2.3 determines if the post-appointment BEP is in response to the HLM’s pre-appointment BEP. In essence this Level 1 Analysis help to determine the basis on whether the Appointing Party will be indeed receiving BIM deliverables in line with the IRs within HLM’ BEP.

Moreover, latest BS EN ISO 19650 standards closely align to oldest BS/PAS 1192 standards and most of the update is around the terminology being used. For that reason, the BEPs’ contents are being verified against the set criteria within BS EN ISO 19650 suite of standards, even though the NMIS project was agreed to be delivered to the oldest suite of BS/PAS 1192 Standards. However, as BS EN ISO 19650 are the latest industry standards being used, it was believed to be more beneficial for the research to use the latest established criteria rather than against the superseded BS/PAS 1192.

3.2.1 Pre-appointment BEP

A first comprehensive plan for a NMIS project aka pre-appointment BEP was created on 02.2019 by HLM Architects out of the UoS' outline brief. For that reason, the below table 14 is set to represent pre-appointment BEP's development against the BS EN ISO 19650 suite of standards:

	PRE-APPOINTMENT BEP CONTENT CRITERIA	DETAILS	RECOMMENDATIONS	INCLUDED
A.	Details of individuals for IM functions	<p>Section 3.1. lists names and contact details of delivery team members assigned to a variety of IM functions from HLM, WSL & DML, with the Contractor to TBC as expected.</p> <p>Section 3.1 clearly describes responsibilities of those functions.</p>	<i>No comment.</i>	YES
B.	Information Delivery Strategy	<p>Appendix A includes RM with LOD/LOI of the content aligned to RIBA Stages.</p> <p>Section 2.3 describes the Collaboration process including details of CDE, Exchange procedures & Resolution of conflicts.</p> <p>Section 3.3 introduces Objectives for the delivery of PIMs</p> <p>Sections 3.6 covers Approval of information.</p> <p>Sections 3.7 defines PIM Authorisation process.</p> <p>Section 5.8 list project deliverables for AIM purposes.</p>	<p><i>- Comprehensive details of how the Delivery Team will meet the IRs and the willingness to meet those IRs are recommended to be included.</i></p> <p><i>- Collaborative goals for the project are recommended to be determined.</i></p> <p><i>- Delivery Team's organisational structure, commercial relationships, and composition of each Task Team are recommended to be examined and included.</i></p>	PARTLY
C.	Federation Strategy	Section 5.1 is described to contain Volume strategy but refers to Section 5.3 that contains file naming strategy and volume definitions.	<i>No comment.</i>	YES
D.	Responsibility Matrix (RM)	Section 4.3 refers to RM in Appendix A, which includes information deliverables for each Discipline.	<i>- RM is recommended to include IM functions.</i>	PARTLY
E. F.	Information Production Methods & Procedures + Project's Information Standard	<p>Section 5.0 defines Standard Method and Procedure, which include the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Volume Strategy - PIM Origin and Orientation - Model Files and Published Document Naming - Layer Naming Conventions - Agreed Modelling Tolerances of PIMs - Presentation of Annotations, Dimensions and Symbols 	<p><i>- Since there are no IRs, methods & procedures are recommended to be fully specified within the BEPs as agreed with the Appointing Party.</i></p> <p><i>- Programme milestones, Responsibilities, formats for expected information at each agreed ie are</i></p>	PARTLY

		<p>- Drawing Sheet Templates - Attribute Data and AIM</p> <p>Section 2.3 defines Collaboration process including Distribution of Information.</p> <p>Section 2.5 includes Quality Assurance and Security requirements & access rights procedures.</p> <p>Section 3.5. provides Existing Legacy Data Use</p> <p>Section 3.6 consist of Approval of Information</p> <p>Section 3.7 describes PIM Authorisation process</p>	<p><i>recommended to be mapped.</i></p>	
G.	Software, Hardware, and IT	<p>Section 4.2 defines Collaboration processes which include Software and its versions for the Delivery Team</p> <p>Section 6.2 lists Model Sharing Formats</p>	<p><i>- Hardware & IT used by the Delivery Team is recommended to be defined.</i></p>	PARTLY

Table 14 – Pre-appointment BEP Audit

3.2.2 Post-appointment BEP

The pre-appointment BEP for a NMIS project was then responded with post-appointment BEP on 12.2020, which was produced by BSL who were appointed by MCL, hence, the below table 15 represents post-appointment BEP's development against the BS EN ISO 19650 suite of standards:

	POST-APPOINTMENT BEP CONTENT CRITERIA	DETAILS	RECOMMENDATIONS	INCLUDED
A.	Details of individuals for IM functions	<p>Section 2.3 lists key BIM personnel.</p> <p>Section 3.1. lists IM functions for Task teams assigned to names and contact details from WSL.</p>	<p>- All IM functions are recommended to be assigned to names with contact details including BSL, HLM & DML.</p> <p>- Responsibilities for IM functions are recommended to be defined.</p>	PARTLY
B.	Information Delivery Strategy	<p>Section 2.4 describes collaborative goals & objectives for the project</p> <p>Section 3.4 contains Project Information Model (PIM) Delivery Strategy.</p> <p>Section 3.5 includes Asset Information Model (AIM) Delivery Strategy.</p> <p>Sections 3.8, 3.10 & 3.11 cover Approval of information and compliance.</p> <p>Sections 7.3, 7.4 & 7.5 list project deliverables.</p>	<p>- Comprehensive details of how the Delivery Team will meet the IRs and the willingness to meet those IRs are recommended to be included.</p> <p>- Level of information is recommended to be defined.</p> <p>- Delivery Team's organisational structure, commercial relationships, and composition of each Task Team are recommended to be examined and included.</p>	PARTLY
C.	Federation Strategy	<p>Section 5.2 defines Zone & Volume/System Strategy, which contains description of Project Volumes as well as file naming strategy in Section 5.6.</p>	<p>- Federation strategy in addition to File naming typically include details and/or graphs of how the 3D PIM will be subdivided within the project to different disciplines e.g., Architectural, Mechanical etc. as well as any further segregations at the model development stage if the agreed size got exceeded for the Task Teams to work together with the seamlessly working Federated models.</p>	PARTLY
D.	Responsibility Matrix (RM)	<p>Section 4.7 states that Designers Responsibilities Matrix is TBC.</p> <p>Section 3.2 contains 'Responsible, Accountable, Consulted & Informed (RACI)' table, in which BSL details that MCL are 'Responsible' to establish the delivery team's detailed RM.</p>	<p>- RM is recommended to include IM functions and either project or asset IM tasks, or information deliverables as appropriate.</p>	PARTLY

3.2.3 Pre-appointment BEP vs Post-appointment BEP

In this chapter the difference between pre & post-appointment BEPs is being analysed within the below table 16 to showcase any variations between these two documents as per chapter 2.6 of literature review. The variations in post-appointment BEP are then being evaluated whether they could be detrimental for UoS during the handover or not:

	BEPs CONTENT	VARIATIONS	COMMENTS	EQUIVALENT
A.	Details of individuals for IM functions	- n/a	- <i>Details of individuals for IM functions are expected to be updated if/when new task teams are appointed.</i>	YES
B.	Information Delivery Strategy	- RM with LOD/LOI - Collaboration process - CDE process - Exchange procedures - Resolution of conflicts - Authorisation process	- <i>Information delivery strategy between two BEPs are expected to be alignment, due to the absence of the UoS IRs, the post-appointment BEP is recommended to follow the pre-appointment BEP, which in turn is representing the UoS' IRs.</i>	NO
C.	Federation Strategy	- none	- <i>no comment.</i>	YES
D.	Responsibility Matrix (RM)	- RM not defined within post-appointment BEP	- <i>RM within pre-appointment BEP is recommended to be as minimum copied over to the post-appointment BEP, including IM functions unless otherwise agreed.</i>	NO
E. F.	Information Production Methods & Procedures + Project's Information Standard	- PIM Origin and Orientation - Drawing Sheet Templates - Collaboration process including Distribution of Information - Quality Assurance - Security requirements & access rights procedures - Existing Legacy Data Use - Approval of Information - PIM Authorisation process	- <i>Most information production methods & procedures as well as project information standards typically follow from the pre-appointment to post-appointment BEP, however, there are instances that some of this information gets updated especially post-appointment. However, post-appointment BEP is expected to be in alignment to Appointing Party's IRs, therefore, if some of the information proposed is different from Appointing Party's expectations, it should be audited and approved. For that reason, the BEP shall be made available for an audit within 6 weeks post-appointment.</i>	NO
G.	Software, Hardware, and IT	- none	- <i>no comment.</i>	YES

Table 16 – Alignment check of Post-appointment BEP against Pre-appointment BEP

3.3 Level 2 Analysis – Lead Appointed Party’s BIM Deliverables

Specific Appointing Party’s expectations for FM purposes commonly include Quality Assurance, COBie requirements, File Naming Conventions, Object & Room Naming Conventions, System performance, Classification and many more, therefore, these typical expectations are being analysed in terms of validating Lead Appointed Party’s WIP BIM deliverables at RIBA Stage 5 for NMIS project in relevance to Appointing Party’s IR in a form of a pre-appointment BEP as well as post-appointment BEP as identified in chapter 2.7 of Literature Review. Most of the times, any validation or audits carried out on projects are driven by IRs, pre-appointment BEP and post-appointment BEP.

The screenshot in figure 7 represents a screenshot of the graphical data within the MEP Information model of the NMIS project, that also incorporates necessary non-graphical data such as COBie for FM purposes, received within both .RVT and .IFC formats. Whereas the pictures in figures 8 & 9 show the interior of the current state of the live NMIS project and display how well the design and coordination within 3D models align with the construction works on site.

Figure 7 – 3D image from the MEP Information Model of the NMIS project at RIBA Stage 5 (IES, 2022)

Figure 8 – Interior of the NMIS project + Information Model of the exact space within Dalux (Juste, 2022)

Figure 9 – Interior of the NMIS project + Information Model of the exact space within Dalux (Juste, 2022)

3.3.1 Information Model – audit

Chapter 3.3.1 displays the NMIS’ MEP Information Model analysis within table 17 below against Appointing Party’s IRs set within the pre-appointment BEP and post-appointment BEP, which have been tabulated with different types of checks against the information from both BEPs and MAL, whilst displaying findings, proposing recommendations & showcasing comparisons as following:

	TYPE OF CHECKS	FINDINGS	IRs (aka BEPs)	COMPARABLE
1	Model File Name:	<p>‘NMIS-IES-ZZ-ZZ-M3-ME-0001.rvt’ ‘NMIS-IES-ZZ-ZZ-M3-ME-0001.ifc’</p> <p>The files naming is not fully corresponding with the BEPs, as following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - undefined Role code ‘ME’ used; - undefined Originator code ‘IES’ used; - incorrect Series number length used of ‘0001’, which should be fixed to 5 digits rather than 4 as it seems that classification and sequence number have not been applied; - Status metadata not included; - Revision metadata not included; - Description metadata not included; 	<p><i>UoS’ file naming requirements are described in section 5.6 within the post-appointment BEP and section 5.3 within the pre-appointment BEP, apart from the additional metadata required within the post-appointment BEP, which is required as following:</i></p> <p>PROJECT-ORIGINATOR-VOLUME-LEVEL-TYPE-ROLE-SERIES NUMBER (CLASSIFICATION + SEQUENCE)_STATUS_REVISION_DESCRIPTION</p> <p><i>e.g. = ‘NMIS-DML-ZZ-ZZ-M3-M-60901_S1_P04_MechanicalMode I’</i></p>	PARTLY
2	Formats supplied:	<p>‘UN-FEDERATED INDIVIDUAL INFORMATION MODEL’:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - .RVT - .IFC <p>‘FEDERATED INFORMATION MODEL’:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - .NWD 	<p><i>UoS’ BIM deliverable requirements that are required to be uploaded to CDE at project milestones by the appointed parties are as per section 5.16 & 6.3 within the post-appointment BEP and sections 4.2 & 6.2 within the pre-appointment BEP, as following:</i></p> <p>‘UN-FEDERATED INDIVIDUAL INFORMATION MODEL’:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - .RVT (or other native) - .IFC <p>‘FEDERATED INFORMATION MODEL’:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NWD 	PARTLY
3	File versions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Revit 2019 - IFC 2x3 	<p><i>The PIM is required to be delivered by the organisations in the following versions as per section 6.1 within the post-appointment BEP and sections 4.2 & 6.1 within the pre-appointment BEP:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REVIT 2019 - IFC 2X3 	YES

4	File sizes:	<p><i>'UN-FEDERATED INDIVIDUAL INFORMATION MODEL':</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - .RVT = 214.1Mb - .IFC = 373.5Mb <p><i>'FEDERATED INFORMATION MODEL':</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - .NWD = unknown <p><i>'COBie DATA':</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - .XLSX = 0.9Mb - .IFC = 373.5Mb 	<p>UoS does not have any explicit system performance requirements in terms of 'size' for models, therefore both BEPs do not have that information defined.</p> <p>Nevertheless, as industry best practice since the system performance is highly important, the BEPs are recommended to contain the proposed information.</p>	N/A
5	Model Warnings:	<p>There have been 3,073 variety of warnings found</p>	<p>As industry best practice, as part of Quality Assurance (QA) & Quality Control (QC) any unresolved model warnings & error messages are recommended to be agreed with NMIS' IM and recorded separately within the post-appointment BEP for each core discipline model.</p>	NO
6	Object duplicates:	<p>There have been 27 identical instances found in the same place</p>	<p>Any duplicates aka identical instances in the same place will result in double counting in quantity schedules and are recommended to be removed from the Information Model / COBie data prior to being shared as industry best practice.</p>	NO
7	Classification Parameters (Uniclass 2015):	<p>7% (3,844) of objects contain Uniclass 2015 code in the following parameter: 'COBie.Type.Category'</p> <p>6% (3,630) of objects contain Uniclass 2015 code & description in the following parameters: 'Classification.Uniclass.Ss.Description' and 'Classification.Uniclass.Ss.Number'</p> <p>Over 90% of objects do not contain Uniclass 2015 classification within any objects' parameters nor objects' naming.</p> <p>0% (0) of systems contain Uniclass 2015 code and description</p>	<p>As per section 5.4. within the post-appointment BEP, the UNICLASS 2015 Classification system is required to be used and applied to all drawings, model objects and systems.</p>	PARTLY
8	Object naming:	<p>'SOURCE_TYPE_SUB-TYPE' = 0% of model objects follow this format</p> <p>'ROLE'_ 'CLASSIFICATION'_ 'PRESENTATION'_ 'SOURCE'_ 'TYPE'_ 'SUBTYPE' = 0% of model objects follow this format</p>	<p>As per section 7.4. within the post-appointment BEP and 5.7 within the pre-appointment BEP, provision of BIM objects naming is required to be to BS854-1 and/or NBS BIM Object Standard, which is recommended to be either of the following formats: 'SOURCE'_ 'TYPE'_ 'SUBTYPE'</p>	NO

		SPACES & CHARACTERS = there are spaces and characters remaining in both Family 'Names' & Family 'Types'	or; 'ROLE' 'CLASSIFICATION' 'PRESENTATION' 'SOURCE' 'TYPE' 'SUBTYPE'																									
9	Total no. of Objects:	There have been 57,725 objects found	<i>No specific requirements.</i>	N/A																								
10	Levels / Storeys naming:	The level codes and description found are as follow: <table border="0"> <thead> <tr> <th>'LEVEL CODE'</th> <th>'DESCRIPTION'</th> <th>'LEVEL CODE'</th> <th>'DESCRIPTION'</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>L00</td> <td>nil</td> <td>FN</td> <td>Foundations</td> </tr> <tr> <td>L01</td> <td>nil</td> <td>00</td> <td>Ground floor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>L02</td> <td>nil</td> <td>01</td> <td>First Floor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>RF</td> <td>nil</td> <td>02</td> <td>Second Floor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>L01 Plant</td> <td>nil</td> <td>RF</td> <td>Roof Level</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	'LEVEL CODE'	'DESCRIPTION'	'LEVEL CODE'	'DESCRIPTION'	L00	nil	FN	Foundations	L01	nil	00	Ground floor	L02	nil	01	First Floor	RF	nil	02	Second Floor	L01 Plant	nil	RF	Roof Level	<i>Level naming convention is required as per section 5.2.3 of the pre-appointment BEP:</i>	PARTLY
'LEVEL CODE'	'DESCRIPTION'	'LEVEL CODE'	'DESCRIPTION'																									
L00	nil	FN	Foundations																									
L01	nil	00	Ground floor																									
L02	nil	01	First Floor																									
RF	nil	02	Second Floor																									
L01 Plant	nil	RF	Roof Level																									
11	Levels / Storeys 'Elevations':	Elevation markers = 5 x elevation markers found within the model, and 4 elevation heights are the same as specified within the pre-appointment BEP; Elevation base = from 'Project Base Point'; Missing levels = 'FN – Foundations', which is often not needed within the MEP model; Additional levels = there is 1 extra elevation called 'L01 Plant', that should not be forming part of COBie;	<i>Agreed elevation levels / storeys were included within the section 5.2.3 of the pre-appointment BEP.</i> <i>'Foundations' elevation is missing as it is not typically required within the MEP model, however it is best practice to copy monitor levels, spaces & grids from the Architectural Model or a setting-up Model as 'copy-monitor' feature provides immediate visual feedback to monitor any slightest of changes to both levels and grids.</i>	PARTLY																								
12	Total no. of Levels:	There have been 5 levels found	<i>There are 5 levels within Section 5.2.3 of the pre-appointment BEP defined, however, 1 level varies slightly with the naming / elevation.</i>	PARTLY																								
13	Model Purge:	The information model has been fully purged and contains 0 unpurged instances	<i>As per sections 5.13.1 and 5.15 within the post-appointment BEP, every model file is required to be purged and compressed prior to issue.</i>	YES																								
14	Units:	The units within the model are as following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Length = mm (to 0 decimal) - Area = m2 (to 0 decimal) - Angle = degrees (to 0 decimal) - Volume = m3 (to 2 decimal) 	<i>The Units defined within the section 5.12 within the post-appointment BEP and section 5.7 within the pre-appointment BEP are required as following:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Length = mm (to 0 decimal) - Area = m2 (to 1 decimal) - Angle = degrees (to 2 decimal) - Volume = m3 (to 1 decimal) 	PARTLY																								
15	References / file links:	The model has been cleaned from all the Revit/IFC/CAD links prior to issue	<i>As per sections 5.13.1 and 5.15 within the post-appointment BEP, every model file is required to be cleaned from references/ file links prior to issue.</i>	YES																								

16	<p>Coordinates: Project Base Point & Survey Point</p>	<p>Project Base Point: The coordinates of Eastings and Northings as well as the Angle to true North of Project Base Point have been set within the MEP model as per the post-appointment BEP.</p> <p>Survey Point: No information defined.</p>	<p><i>As per section 5.3. within the post-appointment BEP, location and orientation of virtual Information Models are required to remain consistent throughout the lifecycle of the project.</i></p> <p><i>However, the coordinates within section 5.2 of the pre-appointment BEP differ slightly from the post-appointment BEP, therefore, it is assumed that these have been updated mid-through the project to reflect the latest survey.</i></p>	<p>YES</p>
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Table 17 – MEP Information Model Audit against BEPs

3.3.2 COBie Data Sheet – asset data validation

In the absence of the Appointing Party’s IRs, MCL agreed to deliver handover data set based on a COBie data set which is aligned with a typical CAFM software and/or O&M requirements (Bimsense, 2021), hence MCL created a Maintainable Asset List (MAL) of the typical MEP components on the NMIS project, which is validated in the table 18 below:

TYPE OF CHECKS	FINDINGS	IRs (aka MAL)	COMPARABLE
1	<p>COBie File Name: 'NMIS-OPE-ZZ-XX-IE-N-0601_S01_P3.xlsx'</p> <p>The files naming is not fully corresponding with the BEPs, as following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - undefined ROLE code 'N' used; - undefined ORIGINATOR code 'OPE' used; - incorrect SERIES NUMBER length used of '0601', which is recommended to be fixed to 5 digits rather than 4 as it seems that classification and sequence number have not been correctly applied; - STATUS metadata contains additional '0' and should be S1 instead; - DESCRIPTION metadata not included; 	<p>UoS' file naming requirements are described in section 5.6 within the post-appointment BEP and section 5.3 within the pre-appointment BEP, apart from the additional metadata required within the post-appointment BEP, which is required as following:</p> <p>PROJECT-ORIGINATOR-VOLUME-LEVEL-TYPE-ROLE-SERIES NUMBER (CLASSIFICATION + SEQUENCE)_STATUS_REVISION_DESCRIPTION</p> <p>e.g. = 'NMIS-BSL-ZZ-XX-IE-M-00501_S3_P01_COBieDataSheet'</p>	PARTLY
2	<p>Formats supplied: 'COBie DATA':</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - .XLSX - .IFC 	<p>UoS' COBie deliverable requirements that are required to be uploaded to CDE at project milestones by the appointed parties are as per section 5.16 & 6.3 as following:</p> <p>'COBie DATA':</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - .XLSX - .IFC 	YES
3	<p>File versions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IFC 2x3 - COBie UK 2012 	<p>COBie data required to be delivered by the organisations in the following versions as per section 5.16, 6.1 & within the post-appointment BEP:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IFC 2X3 - COBIE UK 2012 	YES
4	<p>Classification Parameters (Uniclass 2015):</p> <p>100% (1) of organisations contain Uniclass 2015 code & description in the requested parameter: COBie 'Category' = 'Contact' tab</p> <p>0% (1) of buildings contain Uniclass 2015 code & description in the requested parameter: COBie 'Category' = 'Facility' tab</p>	<p>As per section 5.4. within the post-appointment BEP, the UNICLASS 2015 Classification system is required to be used and applied to all drawings, model objects and systems. Therefore, Maintainable Asset List (MAL) was created that requests Uniclass Code & description within 'CONTACT',</p>	PARTLY

	<p>0% (215) of spaces contain Uniclass 2015 code & description in the requested parameter: COBie 'Category' = 'Space' tab</p> <p>100% (4,824) of objects contain Uniclass 2015 code & description in the requested parameter: COBie 'Category' = 'Type' tab</p> <p>100% (512) of systems contain Uniclass 2015 code & description in the requested parameter: COBie 'Category' = 'System' tab</p>	<p>'FACILITY', 'SPACE', 'TYPE' & 'SYSTEM' TABS.</p>																									
5	<p>Objects naming (COBie Type tab): 'SOURCE_TYPE_SUB-TYPE' = 0% of 'type' objects follow this format</p> <p>'ROLE'_'CLASSIFICATION'_'PRESENTATION'_'SOURCE'_'TYPE'_'SUBTYPE' = 0% of 'type' objects follow this format</p> <p>SPACES & CHARACTERS = there are spaces and characters remaining in both Family 'Names' & Family 'Types'</p>	<p><i>As per section 7.4. within the post-appointment BEP and 5.7 within the pre-appointment BEP, provision of BIM objects naming is required to be to BS854-1 and/or NBS BIM Object Standard, which is recommended to be either of the following formats:</i></p> <p>'SOURCE'_'TYPE'_'SUBTYPE' or; 'ROLE'_'CLASSIFICATION'_'PRESENTATION'_'SOURCE'_'TYPE'_'SUBTYPE'</p>	NO																								
6	<p>Total no. of maintainable objects: There have been 4,824 objects deemed on a NMIS project as maintainable.</p>	<i>No specific requirements.</i>	N/A																								
7	<p>Level naming - storeys (COBie Floor tab)</p> <p>The level codes and description found are as follow:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>'LEVEL CODE'</th> <th>'DESCRIPTION'</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>nil</td> <td>FN</td> </tr> <tr> <td>nil</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>nil</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>nil</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>nil</td> <td>RF</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	'LEVEL CODE'	'DESCRIPTION'	nil	FN	nil	1	nil	2	nil	3	nil	RF	<p><i>Level naming convention is required to be as per section 5.2.3 of the pre-appointment BEP:</i></p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>'LEVEL CODE'</th> <th>'DESCRIPTION'</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>FN</td> <td>Foundations</td> </tr> <tr> <td>00</td> <td>Ground floor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>01</td> <td>First Floor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>02</td> <td>Second Floor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>RF</td> <td>Roof Level</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	'LEVEL CODE'	'DESCRIPTION'	FN	Foundations	00	Ground floor	01	First Floor	02	Second Floor	RF	Roof Level	NO
'LEVEL CODE'	'DESCRIPTION'																										
nil	FN																										
nil	1																										
nil	2																										
nil	3																										
nil	RF																										
'LEVEL CODE'	'DESCRIPTION'																										
FN	Foundations																										
00	Ground floor																										
01	First Floor																										
02	Second Floor																										
RF	Roof Level																										
8	<p>Levels / Storeys 'Elevations':</p> <p>ELEVATION MARKERS = 5 x elevation markers found within the COBie data sheet</p> <p>ELEVATIONS = are the same as specified within the pre-appointment BEP;</p> <p>ELEVATION BASE = not specified;</p>	<p><i>Agreed elevation levels / storeys were included within the section 5.2.3 of the pre-appointment BEP.</i></p>	YES																								
9	<p>Total no. of Levels: There have been 5 levels found</p>	<p><i>There are 5 levels within Section 5.2.3 of the pre-appointment BEP defined, and those match the ones defined within the COBie data sheet.</i></p>	YES																								
10	<p>Room/Spaces naming: ROOMS' NAMING = inconsistent;</p>	<p><i>Room references do not conform to UoS requirements (accidental derogation). Although,</i></p>	NO																								

	(COBie Space tab)	There have been 3 x different naming conventions used as following: - NM101 - STR01/02 - RSR/01/01	<i>room/space naming convention has not been specified within neither the pre-appointment BEP & post-appointment BEP, the convention used is as minimum required to be consistent across all rooms on the NMIS project.</i>	
11	Total no. of Spaces:	There have been 215 spaces found	<i>No specific requirements.</i>	N/A
12	COBie data sheet tabs:	9 x tabs were included within the COBie data sheet as per MCL's MAL as shown below: 'INSTRUCTION' 'CONTACT' 'FACILITY' 'FLOOR' 'SPACE' 'ZONE' 'TYPE' 'COMPONENT'	<i>COBie tabs required to be included as per COBie Matrix within MCL's MAL as following: 'INSTRUCTION' 'CONTACT' 'FACILITY' 'FLOOR' 'SPACE' 'ZONE' 'TYPE' 'COMPONENT'</i>	YES
13	COBie tab: 'Contact'	There are 9 x columns as per MCL's MAL, and these have been populated/not populated as identified below: EMAIL - populated CREATEDBY - populated CREATEDON - populated CATEGORY - populated COMPANY - populated PHONE - populated EXTSYSTEM - unsuitable EXTOBJECT - as n/a EXTIDENTIFIER - populated	<i>'CONTACT' tab is required to include populated columns with COBie data as agreed in MCL's MAL, as following: EMAIL CREATEDBY CREATEDON CATEGORY COMPANY PHONE EXTSYSTEM EXTOBJECT EXTIDENTIFIER</i>	YES
14	COBie tab: 'Facility'	There are 21 x columns as per MCL's MAL, and these have been populated/not populated as identified below: NAME - populated CREATEDBY - populated CREATEDON - populated CATEGORY - as N/A PROJECTNAME - as N/A SITENAME - as N/A LINEARUNITS - populated AREAUNITS - populated VOLUMEUNITS - populated CURRENCYUNITS - populated AREAMEASUREMENT - populated EXTERNALSYSTEM - populated EXTPROJECTOBJECT - populated EXTPROJECTIDENTIF - populated EXTSITEOBJECT - populated EXTSITEIDENTIFIER - populated EXTFACILITYOBJECT - populated EXTFACILITYIDENTIF - populated DESCRIPTION - as N/A PROJECTDESCRIPTION - as N/A SITEDescription - as N/A	<i>'FACILITY' tab is required to include populated columns with COBie data as agreed in MCL's MAL, as following: NAME CREATEDBY CREATEDON CATEGORY PROJECTNAME SITENAME LINEARUNITS AREAUNITS VOLUMEUNITS CURRENCYUNITS AREAMEASUREMENT EXTERNALSYSTEM EXTPROJECTOBJECT EXTPROJECTIDENTIFIER EXTSITEOBJECT EXTSITEIDENTIFIER EXTFACILITYOBJECT EXTFACILITYIDENTIFIER DESCRIPTION PROJECTDESCRIPTION SITEDescription</i>	PARTLY

15	COBie tab: 'Floor'	<p>There are 10 x columns as per MCL's MAL, and these have been populated/not populated as identified below:</p> <p>NAME - as N/A CREATEDBY - populated CREATEDON - populated CATEGORY - populated EXTSYSTEM - populated EXTOBJECT - populated EXTIDENTIFIER - populated DESCRIPTION - not as requested ELEVATION - populated HEIGHT - as N/A</p>	<p><i>'FLOOR'</i> tab is required to include populated columns with COBie data as agreed in MCL's MAL, as following:</p> <p>NAME CREATEDBY CREATEDON CATEGORY EXTSYSTEM EXTOBJECT EXTIDENTIFIER DESCRIPTION ELEVATION HEIGHT</p>	PARTLY
16	COBie tab: 'Space'	<p>There are 13 x columns as per MCL's MAL, and these have been populated/not populated as identified below:</p> <p>NAME - inconsistent CREATEDBY - populated CREATEDON - populated CATEGORY - as N/A FLOORNAME - as N/A DESCRIPTION - populated EXTSYSTEM - populated EXTOBJECT - populated EXTIDENTIFIER - populated ROOMTAG - as N/A USABLEHEIGHT - as N/A GROSSAREA - as N/A NETAREA - as N/A</p>	<p><i>'SPACE'</i> tab is required to include populated columns with COBie data as agreed in MCL's MAL, as following:</p> <p>NAME CREATEDBY CREATEDON CATEGORY FLOORNAME DESCRIPTION EXTSYSTEM EXTOBJECT EXTIDENTIFIER ROOMTAG USABLEHEIGHT GROSSAREA NETAREA</p>	NO
17	COBie tab: 'Zone'	<p>There are 9 x columns as per MCL's MAL, and these have been populated/not populated as identified below:</p> <p>NAME - not populated CREATEDBY - not populated CREATEDON - not populated CATEGORY - not populated SPACENAMES - not populated EXTSYSTEM - not populated EXTOBJECT - not populated EXTIDENTIFIER - not populated DESCRIPTION - not populated</p>	<p><i>'ZONE'</i> tab is required to include populated columns with COBie data as agreed in MCL's MAL, as following:</p> <p>NAME CREATEDBY CREATEDON CATEGORY SPACENAMES EXTSYSTEM EXTOBJECT EXTIDENTIFIER DESCRIPTION</p>	NO
18	COBie tab: 'Type'	<p>There are 20 x columns as per MCL's MAL, and these have been populated/not populated as identified below:</p> <p>NAME - naming not to BS 8541-1 CREATEDBY - populated CREATEDON - populated CATEGORY - populated DESCRIPTION - populated ASSETTYPE - populated MANUFACTURER - some as N/A MODELNUMBER - as N/A WARRANTYGUARANTORPA - as N/A</p>	<p><i>'TYPE'</i> tab is required to include populated columns with COBie data as agreed in MCL's MAL, as following:</p> <p>NAME CREATEDBY CREATEDON CATEGORY DESCRIPTION ASSETTYPE MANUFACTURER MODELNUMBER</p>	PARTLY

		<p>WARRANTYDURATIONPA - as N/A WARRANTYGUARANTORLA - as N/A WARRANTYDURATIONLA - as N/A WARRANTYDURATIONUN - as N/A EXTSYSTEM - populated EXTOBJECT - populated EXTIDENTIFIER - populated NOMINALENGTH - as N/A NOMINALWIDTH - as N/A NOMINALHEIGHT - as N/A MODELREFERENCE - as N/A</p>	<p>WARRANTYGUARANTORPARTS WARRANTYDURATIONPARTS WARRANTYGUARANTORLABOR WARRANTYDURATIONLABOR WARRANTYDURATIONUNIT EXTSYSTEM EXTOBJECT EXTIDENTIFIER NOMINALENGTH NOMINALWIDTH NOMINALHEIGHT MODELREFERENCE</p>	
19	COBie tab: 'Component'	<p>There are 13 x columns as per MCL's MAL, and these have been populated/not populated as identified below: NAME - populated CREATEDBY - populated CREATEDON - populated TYPENAME - populated SPACE - as N/A DESCRIPTION - as N/A EXTSYSTEM - populated EXTOBJECT - populated EXTIDENTIFIER - populated SERIALNUMBER - as N/A INSTALLATIONDATE - as N/A WARRANTYSTARTDATE - as N/A TAGNUMBER - as N/A</p>	<p><i>'COMPONENT' tab is required to include populated columns with COBie data as agreed in MCL's MAL, as following:</i></p> <p>NAME CREATEDBY CREATEDON TYPENAME SPACE DESCRIPTION EXTSYSTEM EXTOBJECT EXTIDENTIFIER SERIALNUMBER INSTALLATIONDATE WARRANTYSTARTDATE TAGNUMBER</p>	NO
20	COBie tab: 'System'	<p>There are 9 x columns as per MCL's MAL, and these have been populated/not populated as identified below: NAME - populated CREATEDBY - populated CREATEDON - populated CATEGORY - populated COMPONENTNAMES - populated EXTSYSTEM - populated EXTOBJECT - populated EXTIDENTIFIER - populated DESCRIPTION - populated</p>	<p><i>Columns in 'SYSTEM' tab have not been deemed as required within MCL's MAL.</i></p>	YES

Table 18 – COBie Data Sheet validation against BEPs & MAL

3.3.3 Information Model vs COBie Data Sheet vs MAL

Chapter 3.3.3 identifies whether the COBie data sheet was automatically exported directly from an Information model as specified in section 5.16 of the post-appointment BEP or the data was manually populated within the excel COBie data spreadsheet as opposed to within the Information model, as displayed in table 19 below:

TYPE OF CHECKS	FINDINGS	COMMENTS	COMPARABLE
1	<p>Model's COBie vs MAL:</p> <p>Having reviewed the Information model against the MAL, and the following accessories/equipment were populated with information and deemed as maintainable assets:</p> <p>SANITARY APPLIANCES - no SERVICES EQUIPMENT - no REFUSE DISPOSAL - no WATER SUPPLY - yes SPACE HEATING & COOLING - yes VENTILATION & AIR COND- yes ELECTRICAL POWER - yes LIGHTING - yes SAFETY & PROTECTION - yes</p>	<p><i>MAL was agreed by MCL, and what was deemed as maintainable assets and requested to be included within both Information Model and COBie data sheet are the following accessories & equipment:</i></p> <p>SANITARY APPLIANCES SERVICES EQUIPMENT REFUSE DISPOSAL WATER SUPPLY SPACE HEATING & COOLING VENTILATION & AIR CONDITION ELECTRICAL POWER LIGHTING SAFETY & PROTECTION</p>	PARTLY
2	<p>COBie data sheet vs MAL:</p> <p>Having reviewed the COBie Data Sheet against the MAL, and the following accessories/equipment were populated with information and deemed as maintainable assets:</p> <p>SANITARY APPLIANCES - no SERVICES EQUIPMENT - no REFUSE DISPOSAL - no WATER SUPPLY - yes SPACE HEATING & COOLING - yes VENTILATION & AIR COND- yes ELECTRICAL POWER - yes LIGHTING - yes SAFETY & PROTECTION - yes</p>	<p><i>MAL was agreed by MCL, and what was deemed as maintainable assets and requested to be included within the COBie data sheet are the following accessories & equipment:</i></p> <p>SANITARY APPLIANCES SERVICES EQUIPMENT REFUSE DISPOSAL WATER SUPPLY SPACE HEATING & COOLING VENTILATION & AIR CONDITION ELECTRICAL POWER LIGHTING SAFETY & PROTECTION</p>	PARTLY
3	<p>Model's COBie vs COBie Data Sheet:</p> <p>Having reviewed the Information model against the COBie data sheet, it seems that most data within COBie data sheet is derived from the Information Model as following:</p> <p>WATER SUPPLY - yes SPACE HEATING & COOLING - yes VENTILATION & AIR COND- yes ELECTRICAL POWER - yes LIGHTING - yes SAFETY & PROTECTION - yes</p>	<p><i>COBie data of all project specific maintainable elements and systems are required to be delivered within the relevant designer's model as per section 5.16 within the post-appointment BEP.</i></p> <p><i>Populating all project specific maintainable elements and systems data is required to occur within Information models and the generation of the COBie export is recommended to occur automatically via COBie plugin from each Information model. If both model and COBie data sheet are populated separately, the information between the model and data sheet show variations.</i></p>	YES

4	Model's COBie Schedules:	<p>Yes - COBie schedules remain within the model, and 5050 x objects were populated with the COBie information as follow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 'INSTRUCTION' – n/a - 'CONTACT' – n/a - 'FACILITY' – n/a - 'FLOOR' – included - 'SPACE' – included - 'ZONE' – not included - 'TYPE' – included - 'COMPONENT' – included - 'SYSTEM' – included 	<p><i>COBie tabs required to be included as per COBie Matrix within MCL's MAL as following:</i></p> <p>'INSTRUCTION' 'CONTACT' 'FACILITY' 'FLOOR' 'SPACE' 'ZONE' 'TYPE' 'COMPONENT'</p>	PARTLY
5	COBie Data Sheet:	<p>Refer to chapter 4.3.2, point 12</p>	<p><i>Refer to chapter 4.3.2, point 12</i></p>	YES
6	COBie Data Sheet vs Model's COBie:	<p>Yes - COBie schedules remain within the model</p> <p>Number of objects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information Model = 3,525 - COBie Data Sheet = 4,824 <p>Number of systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information Model = 1,302 - COBie Data Sheet = 512 <p>Elements populated with the COBie data between Information Model & COBie data sheet are as following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 'INSTRUCTION' – n/a - 'CONTACT' – n/a - 'FACILITY' – n/a - 'FLOOR' – Information model's COBie schedules do not match COBie data sheet = all Model's COBie schedules are empty - 'SPACE' – Information model's COBie schedules do not match COBie data sheet = all Model's COBie schedules are empty - 'ZONE' – both Information model & COBie data sheet are empty - 'TYPE' – Information model's COBie schedules look partially populated, but do not fully match COBie data sheet - 'COMPONENT' – Information model's COBie columns within schedules are populated exactly as within COBie data sheet, however, there are 1299 more objects within COBie data sheet - 'SYSTEM' – Information model's COBie schedules look somewhat populated and do not match COBie data sheet 	<p><i>COBie schedules within the Information model and tabs within COBie data sheet are required to be delivered in alignment to COBie Matrix as well as Asset Schedule within MCL's MAL.</i></p>	NO

Table 19 – Asset Validation between Information Model, COBie Data Sheet and MAL

3.4 Future projects Guidance

In an ideal world scenario, the below list of BIM activities would be carried out by Appointing Parties, Lead Appointed Party, Task Teams at exact RIBA stages. However, RIBA stages are purely dependent on the form of appointment and the ones listed in the table 20 below are indicative. Nevertheless, appropriate RIBA stages are highly important so that BIM processes and technologies are implemented at the right time in the right place to meet a specific purpose on a project. To fill the gap in the Literature review, the below guide in table 20, lists typical BIM activities for perfect FM deployment. These activities ought to take place during the whole lifecycle, from the outset of a project, continuously through Design, Construction and O&M of a facility/infrastructure:

	RIBA PoW STAGES 2020	BIM ACTIVITIES
RESPONSIBILITY = APPOINTING PARTY OR DELEGATED COMPETENT INDIVIDUAL		
1.	Stage 0 or 1	Appoint a dedicated individual/team of BIM specialists (to fulfil Appointing Party's IM function)
2.	Stage 0 or 1	Provide plan for training in place for Facilities Managers, but also for other personnel to increase the knowledge of BIM
3.	Stage 0 or 1	Define IRs (EIR, OIR, AIR & PIR, IDP, Sample COBie data Sheet etc.)
4.	Stage 0 or 1	Consult necessary key organisational Stakeholders (especially Facilities Managers) to support IRs production
5.	Stage 1 or 2	Establish the CDE for the project for the whole lifecycle of a project
6.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Include IRs along with completed Information Protocol at Tender
7.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Request Pre-appointment/Post-Appointment BEPs
8.	Stage 2 or 3	Publish Project Directory
9.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Review of Delivery Team's Capability and Capacity
10.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Audit Pre-appointment/Post-Appointment BEPs
11.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Approval of the Pre-appointment/Post-Appointment BEPs
12.	Stage 3 & 4	Prepare and agree with Appointed Parties the ADR (MAL, Level of Information Need, COBie Schema, RM Matrix etc.)
13.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Audit Information Models (Architectural, MEP, Structural & any other specialists) – to check alignment with IRs
14.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Audit PIM
15.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Validate Asset Data (COBie)
16.	Stage 5 or 6	Final Acceptance/Approval of all BIM Deliverables
RESPONSIBILITY = LEAD APPOINTED PARTY or APPOINTED IM or LEAD DESIGNER		
17.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Nominate a dedicated individual/team of BIM specialists (to fulfil Project IM function)
18.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Familiarise with Appointing Party's IRs and complete Information Protocol
19.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Issue Capability & Capacity Assessment to Task Teams
20.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Assess each Task Teams' Capability & Capacity and summarise it within the proposed BEP
21.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Establish the Delivery Teams' Mobilisation plan and Risk Register
22.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Prepare Pre-appointment/Post-Appointment BEPs in line with IRs and agree the BEP with the Task Teams
23.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Issue the BEP to the Appointing Party for Audit/Approval and cooperate with the Appointing Party to agree the BEP contents
24.	Stage 2	Appoint a surveyor to carry out a Topographical Survey of the land (including 3D BIM Survey)
25.	Stage 2 and/or 3	Produce seed file with real world Coordinates, Grids & levels in an appropriate format and share it with the Task Teams
26.	Stage 2	Set-up BIM Kick-off Meeting

27.	Stage 2	Prepare Project Milestones
28.	Stage 3 & 4	Agree the ADR (MAL, Level of Information Need, COBie Schema, RM Matrix etc.)
29.	Stage 2 or 3	Establish a CDE platform acceptable by the Appointing Party for sharing
30.	Stage 2 & 3 & 4 & 5	Migrate BIM deliverables at each end of RIBA Stage or as otherwise agreed from Lead Appointed Party's CDE into Appointing Party's CDE
31.	Stage 2	Produce a live project programme
32.	Stage 2 & 3 & 4 & 5	Combine TIDPs and produce MIDP - to be shared with the Appointing Party
33.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Carry out Information Models Review and approve prior to sharing with the Appointing Party
34.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Carry out a QA/QC check of Information Models/COBie Data
35.	Stage 2 to 5	Maintain an audit trail of Information handling (via CDE)
36.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Carry out a Coordination Review between all project systems (hard/soft clashes)
37.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Lead regular Coordination & Clash detection meetings
38.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Produce Clash detection reports – to be shared with Task Teams/Appointing Party
39.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Propose resolutions to Coordination and Clashes issues - agree the best outcome
40.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Federate all discipline models and publish PIM
41.	Stage 5 or 6	Federate final as-built discipline models and publish as AIM
RESPONSIBILITY = TASK TEAMS		
42.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Complete Capability & Capacity Assessment forms
43.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Input into Pre-appointment/Post-Appointment BEPs
44.	Stage 3 & 4	Agree the ADR (MAL, Level of Information Need, COBie Schema, RM Matrix etc.)
45.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Check of availability of Reference Information & Shared Resources
46.	Stage 2 and/or 3 and/or 4	Prepare & maintain Task Information Delivery Plan (TIDP)
47.	Stage 2 & 3 & 4 & 5	Produce BIM deliverables in line with TIDPs
48.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Produce geometrical data per each core discipline within Information Models (Architectural, MEP, Structural & any other specialists)
49.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Populate non-geometrical COBie data including classifications and other required data into objects within Information Models in line with MAL
50.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Export COBie data from an Information Model into Spreadsheet as per COBie Schema
51.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Export 2D GA layouts from an Information Model (as required)
52.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Information Review prior to issue
53.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Carry out Clash detection on an Information Model within each Task Team and solve as many coordination issues as possible prior to sharing
54.	Stage 3 & 4 & 5	Quality Assurance (QA) Information Container Check

Table 20 – Guidance to implementing BIM for accurate deployment of FM from the outset of a project

In essence, if none of the above steps are omitted, the received data at the end of every ie in line with RIBA Stages, are required to be in alignment with Appointing Party's expectations. Those BIM Activities performed will not purely improve design, but will enhance inception, capital phase procurement and delivery, asset and facility management, maintenance, refurbishment, and an asset's disposal. This guide in essence endeavours to fill the gap in the Literature review and lists how, by whom and when specific BIM activities should be performed for better FM.

4.0 DISCUSSING ANALYSES

This section discusses what gap analyses in chapter 3.0 mean and how the aim & objectives of this research are achieved. For that reason, several audits of Appointing Party's & Lead Appointed Party's BIM Deliverables on the NMIS project are carried out to identify gaps relating to BIM, FM & IRs. These analyses eventually enabled to produce a guidance for future projects in relevance to the gap within the current Literature as per chapter 2.0.

Accordingly, Level 1 analysis in chapter 3.1 & 3.2 as well as Level 2 analysis in chapter 3.3 helped to determine the basis on whether the Appointing Party is receiving all data in alignment to their expectations. Unfortunately, chapter 3.1 – Level 1 analysis could not be undertaken as Appointing Party's IR suite of documents were never defined and included at the outset of a project, as justified in chapter 2.4 of the literature review. This chapter also answers two of the research questions regarding the insufficient IRs being defined & not included at the outset of a project and within the Lead Appointed Parties' appointment suite of documents to utilise the Lead Appointed Party's BIM deliverables post-handover for O&M purposes. Having said that, in absence of Appointing Party's IR documents, it was agreed that the pre-appointment BEP and 'works information' takes precedence. For that reason, particularly pre-appointment & post-appointment BEPs were analysed in chapter 3.2 against the criteria specified in the Literature review within whole chapter 2.0.

First, chapter 3.2.1 & 3.2.2 revealed that both BEPs partially included typical BEP contents as per chapter 2.6 of the literature review, that are called for within the UK BIM Framework and BS EN ISO 19650 suite of standards. In addition, when comparing both BEPs against each other in chapter 3.2.3, it appears that the post-appointment BEP is partially comparable with the pre-appointment BEP. This signifies that the current state of the live post-appointment BEP does not contain sufficient details to support the delivery of BIM deliverables. However, this does not necessarily mean that the Appointing Party is not receiving the project information to some of their expectations. Though, it should be noted that if some of the information proposed within the post-appointment BEP differs from Appointing Party's IRs aka pre-appointment BEP, the BEP ought to have been made available for an audit, so that the Appointing Party could respond to changes proposed. However, it is unknown whether the audit and agreement of the post-appointment BEP took place.

Furthermore, Level 2 analysis within chapter 3.3 on the other hand showcase gap analysis of some of the BIM deliverables on the NMIS project as established in chapter 2.5 of the literature review. As part of the BIM deliverables review, the selected BIM deliverables were audited as per some industry required checks as defined in chapter 2.7 of the literature review. The chosen MEP Information Model within chapter 3.3.1 was settled to be in partial correspondence to the BEPs because of the following items: File naming convention, Model Warnings, Object duplicates Classification Parameters of Uniclass 2015, Object naming, Levels' naming, Levels' Elevations, no. of Levels and Units. Furthermore, another important deliverable analysed was a federated COBie data sheet, which was also partially alike as the following aspects were not as defined within the BEPs/MAL: COBie File Name Classification Parameters of Uniclass 2015, Objects naming, Level naming, Room naming and COBie tabs. Ultimately, when comparing the MEP Information Model vs COBie Data Sheet vs MAL, it was established that the data was partially aligned with MAL and also some data was manually populated within the COBie Data Sheet as opposed to being automatically imported from the Information Model, which is presenting contradictory information within model in comparison to the data sheet. Regretfully, it means that the current state at mid-Stage 5 of both MEP Information Model as well as COBie Data sheet are in partial alignment with the post-appointment BEP. Having said that, the analyses are based on WIP information available at the time of undertaking the research and the absent information may now be available albeit it is too late for the purpose of this research.

Considering, that these BIM deliverables are still WIP and are not yet end of stage 5 deliverables, in which case gaps in data are anticipated, and inconsistency is regularly expected to be corrected by handover. Consequently, BIM deliverables being published at end of RIBA Stage 5 to the Appointing Party are required to be in alignment with IRs on a typical project or with both BEPs and MAL and as agreed coordinated with a typical CAFM software and/or O&M requirements on the NMIS project. Having said that, to meet the aim, objectives and fill the gaps of this research a guidance is demonstrated in chapter 3.4 with regards to implementing BIM for accurate deployment of FM from the outset of a project.

5.0 CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

This research aimed to carry out an audit of selected BIM Deliverables on the NMIS project to identify gaps in relation to Building Information Modelling (BIM), Facilities Management (FM) & Client's Information Requirements (IRs). The aim is accomplished by a set of objectives, which included current literature review of BIM, FM & IRs, comparison of Pre-appointment BIM Execution Plan (BEP) vs Post-appointment BEP, whilst carrying out an audit of BIM Deliverables on the NMIS project. Therefore, the aim and objectives allowed to fulfil the literature gap and enabled to produce a guidance with regards to BIM, FM & IRs to aid future projects for better FM deployment. In essence, the pragmatic qualitative results from collecting information via e-mails and meetings on a live NMIS project revealed that there were no sufficient IR documents defined to utilise Contractor's BIM deliverables post-handover for operational & maintenance purposes. Outline brief was found to be the solely 'IR' included within the Design Teams' appointment at the outset of a project from which a Pre-appointment BEP was produced, whereas Contractor's appointment suite of documents included Pre-appointment BEP as well as the Design pack aka Works information. Moreover, during examination of the collected information from the NMIS project, the current state at mid-construction phase of the post-appointment BEP is found to contain limited details to support the delivery of BIM deliverables. Likewise, the Building Services 3D BIM Model as well as COBie Data sheet, which both define information for 'as constructed' assets have been delivered in partial alignment with the post-appointment BEP. In addition, the comparison between the Building Services 3D BIM Model against the COBie data sheet and MAL also revealed partial agreement.

Nevertheless, due to time constraints the study was limited to audit of merely work in progress information rather than end of Construction phase information, which at the time of undertaking the research commonly revealed considerable amount of absent information. Even though, the end of construction information on the NMIS project might soon be available and from experience it is fair to say that most of the absent information is likely completed by the end of construction phase, unfortunately it is too late for the purpose of this research. Having said that, this research could have been improved by having two information sets reviewed of mid-construction phase as well as the end of construction phase to compare how much information change and whether it is fully populated and published by the completion of construction works or not.

Since BIM could improve every aspect of a project and not simply design or construction, collectively the construction industry could improve BIM implementation during the whole lifecycle of projects and complete activities by responsible parties at the agreed stages. For that reason, this research paper recommends utilising the guidance suggested in chapter 3.4 by Clients, Contractors & Design Teams, so that received information at the end of every project phase is in alignment with Client's expectations to better operate & maintain their facility/infrastructure. It is through a consistent to a planned approach throughout following the proposed guidance within this research at each project phase, that will ultimately transform construction sector from mostly utilising BIM for Design & Construction to one that is implementing BIM from the outset of a project, continuously through Design, Construction and Operation & Maintenance of the facility/infrastructure.

Finally, to sum-up the intention of this research was to investigate BIM deliverables for better FM deployment in line with the latest BS EN ISO 19650, as superseded BS/PAS 1192 standards have been analysed in the past, hence it was redundant for the purpose of this research. Therefore, Gap analyses specifically within chapter 3.2 might be demonstrating partial alignment to BS EN ISO 19650 but could be in full alignment to agreed BS/PAS 1192, however this was not verified.

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